

HUMAN-CENTRIC AI-ENABLED EXTENDED REALITY APPLICATIONS FOR THE
INDUSTRY 5.0 ERA

D7.3 – DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION,
STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

Lead Beneficiary	INNOV
Work Package Ref.	WP7 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Ecosystem Building
Task Ref.	T7.1 – Dissemination and Communication Activities T7.2 Clustering and Pre-Normative Standardisation Activities T7.4 Community and Ecosystem Building
Deliverable Title	D7.3 – Dissemination, Communication, Standardisation Activities
Due Date	2025-12-31
Delivered Date	2025-12-31
Revision Number	1.0
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Type	Report (R), Other (ORDP)
Document Status	Release
Review Status	Internally Reviewed and Quality Assurance Reviewed
Document Acceptance	WP Leader Accepted and Coordinator Accepted
EC Project Officer	Marta PALAU FRANCO

HORIZON-CL4-2023 Research and Innovation Action

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement no 101135209.

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REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Partner(s)	Description
0.1	2025-10-12	INNOV	Initial Version of Table of Contents (<i>2 months before due date</i>)
0.11	2025-12-01	INNOV	Introductory Paragraph; First version of Section 2
0.13	2025-12-02	INNOV	Outline of Dissemination Activities and Achievements; First version of Section 3, 4
0.14	2025-12-03	INNOV	Presentation of the BeyondXR Activities with other XR projects; First version of Section 5
0.15	2025-12-04	INNOV	First Version of Section 6 and Section 8
0.16	2025-12-06	INNOV, All partners	Additional Inputs to Chapter 2,3,4,5,6,8
0.17	2025-12-08	INNOV, All partners	Updates to Chapters 1,2,3,4,5,6,8
0.18	2025-12-12	INNOV	Updates to Chapters 1,2,3,4,5,6,8 about dissemination, publications and partner activities
0.19	2025-12-13	INNOV	Initial version of Conclusions Section
0.20	2025-12-15	TOG	Updates to Standards-related input (Chapter 7)
0.31	2025-12-12	INNOV	Internal Quality Control; Updates to various sections and formatting
0.32	2025-12-13	INNOV	Formatting and Various Edits; 1 st Complete Draft Version of the Deliverable
0.33	2025-12-18	INNOV	Internal Quality Control; Updates to various sections and formatting; Version for Quality Assurance
0.34	2025-12-29	INNOV, ATB	Updates and Revisions based on ATB's review
0.35	2025-12-29	INNOV, UPRC	Updates and Revisions based on UPRC's review
0.9	2025-12-29	INNOV	Addressing the comments of the reviewers; Inclusion of the new Lessons Learnt Section
1.0	2025-12-30	INNOV	Preparation of Version for Submission; Sent to the Project coordinator

¹ Lead Beneficiary, Contributor, Internal Reviewer, Quality Assurance

² Can be left void

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDA	Attention – Interest – Desire – Action
AIOTI	Alliance for AI, IoT and Edge Continuum Innovation
AR	Augmented Reality
ATEC	Annual Training and Education Conference
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique)
CET	Central European Time
CTA	Call to Action
DAIRO	Data AI and Robotics
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoA	Description of Action
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
ESDC	European Security and Defence College
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
F2F	Face to Face
GA	Grant Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CTR	Click-Through Rate
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electric and Electronic Engineers
INCITS	International Committee for Information Technology Standards
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LNCS	Lecture Notes in Computer Science
MR	Mixed Reality
OA	Open Access
OMG	Object Management Group
QR	Quick Response
ROI	Return on Investment
UC	Use Case
SDO	Standards Development Organizations
TBA	To Be Announced
TOC	Table of Contents
TOG	The Open Group
UC	Use Case
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides a report on the dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities of the Horizon Europe XR5.0 project during the second year (M13–M24) of the project's lifetime. It is the second release of the project's living report on the Dissemination, Communication and Standardisation Activities. The activities of the second year of the project's lifetime have been carried out in-line with the strategy established in the first year and have built on the respective activities of the first year of the project. As part of these activities the consortium intensified its dissemination and outreach efforts. Most importantly, the project has strengthened and reinforced the impact of activities of the first year, such as the project's collaboration with other EU-funded projects on Extended Reality.

One major area of focus of the dissemination and communication activities of the second year of the project has been the expansion of XR5.0's public presence through updated branding materials, enriched communication assets, and strengthened digital channels. The project website nearly doubled its users'/visitors' base when compared to the first year of the project. Moreover, the XR5.0 social media footprint continued to grow steadily as a result of the project's regular and consistent posting of quality content, but also as a result of the partners' coordinated dissemination efforts. Most importantly, the social media channels of the project have benefitted from increased engagement from members from the broader XR community such as members of the BeyondXR cluster. The XR5.0 blog production rate has expanded significantly: Twenty-five new blog posts covering many different XR5.0 related themes were published, which reflected the consortium's commitment towards explaining technical progress, sharing insights, and raising awareness of Industry 5.0 based XR innovations.

Scientific dissemination also accelerated during the second year of the project. Specifically, seven (7) new conference papers were produced by partners and presented at recognised international venues. These papers reflect both the technical readiness of key components and the project's growing contribution to the XR and AI research communities. Moreover, the production of open-access publications remained a guiding principle for the project's publication strategy towards ensuring that all research outcomes are accessible to the wider XR/AI scientific communities. Specifically, all the scientific publications of the project during the second year of the project are accessible as Open Access publications through the project's website and the project's community in the Zenodo platform.

The project's participation and contribution to workshops, conferences, webinars, and live demonstrations also played an important role in strengthening engagement with industrial and academic stakeholders. During the second year of the project, partners participated in a wide range of dissemination events, from technical conferences and innovation summits to local demonstrations and international forums. Most importantly, close to the end of the year, the project initiated a series of webinars that are dedicated to presenting and showcasing the outcomes of the project's pilots. Overall, one webinar session was organized during the second year of the project, which complemented a face to face pilot workshop. These activities have provided insights into the project's human-centric XR solutions and their practical relevance in industrial environments. This webinar series is planned to continue at an intensified pace during the third year of the project's lifetime, as five (5) additional webinars are already planned.

The second year further marked the consolidation and expansion of the BeyondXR cluster, which has been established with XR5.0 in a leading role as the cluster was established as an XR5.0-led initiative during 2024. The activities of the cluster where XR5.0 has actively participated include monthly meetings, shared branding-marketing-dissemination activities, coordinated posts, and the organisation of several impact joint webinars including 3 webinars that were organized during the second year of the project. Overall, with the active contribution of XR5.0, BeyondXR has become a visible and collaborative space for knowledge exchange, community building, and joint outreach within the European XR ecosystem.

In the standards developments and contributions front, XR5.0 has advanced in two fronts: (i) The establishment of liaisons and collaborations with relevant standards development organizations and initiatives; and (ii) The identification of standards-related contributions that can be produced based on the project's results.

XR5.0 maintains a stakeholders' database, which includes stakeholders' that have interacted and/or engaged with XR5.0 through different channels (touch points) such as newsletters, social media, participation in webinars, as well as networking during physical events. The number of stakeholders in this database has expanded significantly during the second year of the project. It comprises over 760 entries which is above the originally set target for the second year of the project's lifetime. This demonstrates the project's ability to attract and engage with its target audiences, which is an asset for the implementation of the project's dissemination and exploitation strategy both during and after the XR5.0 lifetime.

Overall, the dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities of the second year have progressed in alignment with the project's DoA and KPIs. At the same time, they have established a sound basis for the stage for intensified outreach, expanded scientific dissemination, and deeper community engagement during the project's final year.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Objectives, Scope and Purpose

This deliverable reports on the dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities conducted during the second year of the XR5.0 project (M13–M24). It constitutes the second report in the series of annual dissemination deliverables and builds on the strategy and operational framework defined in D7.1 and implemented throughout Year 1 as detailed in D7.2 of the project. During the second year of the project, XR5.0 entered a more mature technological development phase, where key technical components advanced significantly, pilots evolved toward demonstrable outcomes, and where several innovations have been improved and substantiated. This maturation has inevitably increased the need for targeted communication and stakeholder engagement.

The project has also advanced the build up of its ecosystems, which one of the central objectives of XR5.0. Specifically, the project targets the creation of a vibrant ecosystem of engaged actors around its human-centric, AI-enabled XR technologies. To this end, XR5.0 follows the AIDA (Attention – Interest – Desire – Action) methodology which guides the progression from awareness-raising toward active stakeholder engagement and eventual adoption. In Year 2, dissemination and communication efforts focused on generating sustained interest through the presentation of more tangible technological achievements, pilot advancements, and early results with industrial relevance. A wide range of activities were implemented through a considerable number of channels with emphasis on digital channels and digital platforms.

This deliverable documents the activities performed across all dissemination and communication fronts, including:

- the creation of new range communication assets and dissemination templates, which were used to support and strengthen the dissemination and communication activities.
- the implementation of a wide range of dissemination activities (e.g., posting of quality content) over electronic communication channels (including the project’s website and social media platforms);
- the production of scientific publications and participation in workshops, conferences, and events;
- the launch of the pilot-focused webinar series;
- the continued development of synergies and joint actions within the BeyondXR cluster;
- the expansion and analysis of the stakeholders’ database; and
- the progress of standardisation-related interactions with relevant stakeholders towards impacting pre-standardization and pre-normative activities.

Apart from reporting on already completed actions, the deliverable presents the planning for the upcoming period (M25–M36). This planning is destined to implement the project’s strategy during the third and last year of the project’s lifetime, in ways that ensure continuity with the DoA, align with KPI targets, and fulfillment of the project’s evolving/growing communication needs.

1.2 Insights from other Tasks and Deliverables

The present deliverable is produced in the scope of the activities of WP7 of the project, which is cross-cutting workpackage i.e., a workpackage that interacts closely with all the project’s activities in order to disseminate their results to appropriate target groups. Hence, the deliverable is relevant to all other deliverables of the project, as it illustrates how the results of these deliverable were disseminated.

The deliverable is more closely linked to deliverable D7.2 which reported the dissemination and communication activities of the first year of the project. Specifically, the deliverable complements the activities reported in D7.2 based on the dissemination work that took place during the second year of the project. At the same time, the deliverable is closely linked to D7.1, which provided the project’s methodology and plan for the implementation of the dissemination, communication and standardization activities.

1.3 Updates with regards to the Previous Version

The present deliverable is the second version/report on the project's dissemination, communication and standardization activities, which follows the first version/report that was released as deliverable D7.2. The present version reports on the activities of the second year of the project (M13-M24), while the earlier version reported on the activities of the first year of the project (M1-M12). Hence, the two deliverables (D7.2, D7.3) are in principles disjoint and without essential overlaps, as they focus on different periods of the project and different sets of activities. Nevertheless, both deliverables are grounded on the same methodology and similar types of activities, which are however carried out with different intensity across the two periods.

1.4 Deliverable Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- **Section 2** presents the branding processes and dissemination materials developed during Year 2, including updates to templates, flyers, banners, and the general project presentation.
- **Section 3** describes the project's communication channels, updates on the website and its analytics, social media performance, newsletters, blog posts, and additional online activities.
- **Section 4** provides an overview of scientific publications produced during the reporting period, partners' participation in workshops and events, and the pilot-focused webinars and training sessions launched in Year 2. It also presents the indicative plan for future publications.
- **Section 5** describes the activities of the BeyondXR cluster, including new projects that joined the cluster, monthly joint meetings, and the organisation of three collaborative webinars.
- **Section 6** outlines the progress of the stakeholders' database, including growth trends and demographic insights.
- **Section 7** summarises the standardisation-related interactions and ongoing liaisons with SDOs and industrial associations.
- **Section 8** concludes the deliverable with a summary of achievements and an outlook on the activities planned for the final year.

2. XR5.0 TEMPLATES AND DISSEMINATION MATERIALS

2.1 XR5.0 Templates

During the second year of the project, the dissemination team expanded the existing set of templates and created additional materials to support the growing communication and dissemination needs of the consortium. Specifically:

- Figure 1 illustrates the whitepaper template, which has been developed for use across the entire consortium. This template provides a clear and structured format for presenting technical insights, pilot-related results, and other in-depth analyses. It is destined to be used for the production of solution-oriented whitepapers for relevant XR5.0 results such as solutions based on the pilots of the project.
- Figure 2, presents the press release template, designed to help all partners communicate project milestones and news consistently and professionally.

Figure 1-Whitepaper Template.

Note that these templates complement the XR5.0 templates that were prepared during the early stages of the project and which have been extensively used as part of the project's dissemination activities.

Figure 2-Press Release Template.

2.2 Dissemination Materials

2.2.1 General Flyer

During the second year of the project, a general XR5.0 promotional flyer (see Figure 3) was created to support dissemination and communication activities across events, workshops, online channels, and partner-level promotional actions.

The front side of the flyer highlights the project’s overarching objective: the development and validation of a human-centric and AI-enabled XR paradigm tailored to Industry 5.0 environments. It features a clear project description, references to the key XR technologies involved (VR, AR, and MR), and a dedicated section encouraging stakeholders to follow the project on social media. A QR code directs readers to the XR5.0 website in order to provide easy access to further information.

The back side of the flyer showcases the six XR5.0 pilots. Each pilot is listed with its title to provide a quick overview of the project’s scope and application domains. As mentioned in D7.2, six different flyers have been already created for each specific pilot. The flyer also displays the logos of all consortium partners, reinforcing the collaborative and multidisciplinary nature of XR5.0.

Overall, the flyer functions as a visually coherent communication asset that has been used by partners throughout the second project year to raise awareness, support outreach activities, and introduce audiences to the project’s value proposition and pilot activities.

Figure 3-General XR5.0 promotional flyer.

2.2.2 General Project’s Presentation

The general XR5.0 presentation serves as a strong dissemination asset for the consortium, offering a clear and structured overview of the project’s vision, objectives, pilots, and expected impact. It provides partners with a solid foundation for preparing their own communication activities and ensures a unified/coherent narrative when representing the project externally. Figure 4 provides a small overview of the XR5.0 presentation.

Figure 4-General Project's Presentation.

2.2.3 Roll-up Banner

In addition to the general flyer creation of the project, a roll-up banner has been also created (see Figure 5). This roll-up banner provides a clear and visually structured overview of the project, which makes it suitable for use in physical dissemination activities where quick, high-level communication is essential.

The top section of the banner features the XR5.0 logo and the project’s overarching message, “A Human-Centric – AI Enabled Paradigm for Extended Reality,” which establishes immediate brand recognition at the in-site events. Below this, the banner highlights the project’s key objectives with accompanying icons, improving readability and visual appeal, including the development of standards-based reference models, the integration of human–AI collaboration paradigms, the use of human digital twins, and the validation of XR solutions in real Industry 5.0 environments.

A dedicated section lists the six XR5.0 pilots, providing visitors with a concise snapshot of the project’s application areas. Next to the pilots, a QR code enables attendees to instantly access more information via the XR5.0 website, facilitating seamless interaction during physical events.

Figure 5-XR5.0 Roll Up Banner.

2.2.4 Visual Banners

As a continuation of the “visual banners” strategy established during the first year of the project, the dissemination and communication team has created a dedicated visual banner for each social media post, newsletter campaign, and website announcement (see Figure 6). The aim of these banners was to handle

the promotion of each occasion with tailored visual material, while maintaining a consistent look, feel, and brand identity it provides a more coherent communication experience. It allows each message to stand out with clarity and purpose towards reinforcing brand recognition across platforms, and ensuring that audiences can easily associate the visual style with XR5.0. This approach also enhances the overall professionalism of the project’s outreach and supports stronger stakeholder engagement across all channels.

Figure 6-XR5.0 Dedicate Visual Banners for news and webinars

2.2.5 Dissemination Materials Effectiveness

The print banners have been used to support the project’s presence in various events (e.g., the Demo Day at the Smart Factory). Note however that their effectiveness in achievement dissemination targets tends to be more limited when compared to digital channels.

3. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS ANALYSIS AND PERFORMANCE

3.1 Website

3.1.1 Website Overview

During the second year of the project, the XR5.0 website has been updated regularly in order to remain fully up to date and to provide structured information about all project activities. Each section enables users and stakeholders to easily access details about upcoming or conducted events (e.g., webinars), the communication kit, outputs from seminars, workshops, and conferences, as well as the blog posts contributed by project partners. The platform offers a user-friendly interface designed to facilitate navigation and ensure that all publicly available material can be retrieved efficiently. Throughout the second year of the project, the website’s content has been further enriched and expanded towards a more engaging user experience and improving access to the project’s results and dissemination resources.

3.1.2 Website Analytics

During the second year of XR5.0, the project’s website continued to grow steadily in visibility and audience engagement. From January to December 2025, the website reached **3,000 active users** (Figure 7), which is almost **double the reach of the first project year (1.6K users)**. The number of new users also increased significantly (2.9K), indicating that the project continued to attract fresh interest from external stakeholders beyond the initial community. As in the first year, the homepage remained the most visited section of the website, accumulating 2.2K views, followed by the general XR5.0 overview page (629 views) and the “News” page (316 views). The “Blog” and “Publications” pages also saw consistent traffic, with 258 and 242 views, respectively, which shows a stable and growing interest in the project’s technical content. Although no single blog post dominated traffic in the way it did during the first project year, the overall distribution of views suggests a broader and more balanced engagement with the different website sections. User **engagement time averaged 1 minute and 19 seconds**, which demonstrates that visitors interacted in several cases meaningfully with the published material.

Figure 7-XR5.0 Y2 Website Analytics

3.2 Social Media Channels

3.2.1 Overview

The XR5.0 social media strategy builds upon the foundations established during the project’s first year. LinkedIn remained as the primary communication channel for engaging stakeholders and disseminating project updates. Social media content has enabled the project to steadily grow a dedicated community

interested in XR technologies, Industry 5.0 applications, and human-centric AI. Throughout the second year, the project's presence has been further strengthened through regular/consistent posting activity that is fully aligned with the originally set KPI of at least three posts per month. Posting is complemented and supported by regular reposts from partners, cluster projects, and relevant EU initiatives (e.g., other Horizon Europe projects through their official LinkedIn accounts).

The project's dissemination team maintains an active posting rhythm towards sharing updates on webinars, conferences, partner achievements, conferences, and workshops. Additionally, activities from the BeyondXR cluster are regularly featured on XR5.0's channels towards enhancing the project's visibility within a broader network of XR-focused EU initiatives, while supporting the cross-marketing strategy of the project's of the BeyondXR cluster.

All social media posts follow a consistent visual identity, using the XR5.0 colour palette and logo to reinforce brand recognition. Each post is accompanied by a fresh, purpose-specific graphic and a clear call-to-action (CTA) that directs users to the XR5.0 website or relevant online events. This ensures that the visual and textual communication remains coherent, professional, and aligned with the project's branding guidelines. During the second year of the project's lifetime, XR5.0 continued using relevant hashtags to improve discoverability and outreach, contributing to a stable and expanding digital footprint. As a result, XR5.0 has fostered the development of a highly engaged community across its main platforms based on interactions that are frequently driven by news articles, events, webinars, and publications shared on the XR5.0 website. Note that LinkedIn is the primary digital channels of the project: It is used much more frequently than other channels and received the highest engagement. This is mainly due to the nature of the XR5.0 project and of its scientific and technological development results, which are more appealing to professional and research/technical-savvy audiences.

 : <https://www.linkedin.com/company/xr5-0-project/>

 : <https://x.com/XR50project>

 : <https://tinyurl.com/yeydc2df>

 : <https://tinyurl.com/4dydeeph>

3.2.2 LinkedIn

The XR5.0 LinkedIn page continued to grow steadily during the second year of the project, reaching around **730 followers as of December 2nd, 2025** (see Figure 8). The posting strategy remained aligned with the **KPI of a minimum of three posts per month**, although the dissemination team consistently exceeded this target by **publishing 5–6 original posts per month**, complemented by additional reposts from partners, cluster initiatives, and related EU projects. In total, **75 original posts** were published during Year 2 (excluding reposts), which reflects the project's active and expanding digital presence (see Figure 9).

The content shared on LinkedIn throughout the year covered a diverse range of topics, including announcements of conferences and webinars, partner achievements, workshops and publications, blog posts authored by consortium members, and updates from the BeyondXR cluster. This variety ensured

continuous engagement with the XR5.0 community and contributed to a stable increase in followers and interactions (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure 8-LinkedIn page and followers-Y2.

To further enhance outreach, the dissemination team keeps sharing posts also in the second year, in LinkedIn groups relevant to the XR, Industry 5.0, AI, and emerging technology domains, such as [Artificial Intelligence Investors Group](#), [Reality Innovators Network](#), [AI VR AR MR XR Metaverse Machine Learning Artificial Intelligence Virtual Reality Data Science Web3](#), and the [BeyondXR](#) community in which XR5.0 holds a moderator role. This targeted distribution allows the project to reach audiences beyond its follower base and increase its visibility in specialised professional circles.

Throughout the second year, the project continued using a consistent set of hashtags, #XR50project #ai #extendedreality #europeanprojects #horizoneu, which contributed to improved discoverability and strengthened the project’s organic growth on the platform. Meanwhile, all project partners and the synergy projects are being tagged in the XR5.0 LinkedIn post to make it easier for everyone to repost.

In addition to posts published on the official page, XR5.0 content was frequently amplified by consortium members through their personal LinkedIn profiles, as well as through posts published by projects of the BeyondXR cluster. These third-party mentions significantly expanded the project’s reach and reinforced the visibility of XR5.0 across the European XR ecosystem.

Figure 9-Sample LinkedIn posts of XR5.0-Y2.

Figure 10-Sample LinkedIn Repost

In terms of LinkedIn statistics for the second year (as depicted in Figure 11), the performance of the XR5.0 social media activities shows a clear positive track compared to the first year. During the period from 1 January 2025 to 2 December 2025 (LinkedIn statistics retrieved on 2 December 2025), the XR5.0 LinkedIn page accumulated **34,199** impressions, reflecting a significant increase in the overall visibility of the project’s online presence. Engagement indicators have also grown steadily, with **1,138 reactions, 43 comments, and 53 reposts**, which underlines a consistent interaction from the community and a stronger interest in the project’s activities, publications, and events.

Focusing on the demographics of XR5.0 LinkedIn followers, the data reveals a well-targeted and professionally relevant audience. As illustrated also in Figure 11, the largest professional group engaging with the XR5.0 content consists of **Business Development professionals (12.4%)**, followed by individuals working in Education (9.8%), Engineering (8.8%), and Research (6.3%). Additional significant segments include professionals in Media and Communication (6.2%), Project and Programme Management (6%), Operations (5.7%), and Sales (4.3%). This distribution reflects the project’s ability to attract stakeholders from both industrial and academic domains, as well as from operational, managerial, and technical roles that are directly aligned with XR5.0’s scope in Industry 5.0, XR technologies, and human-centric AI.

Figure 11-LinkedIn Statistics.

Compared to the first year, as Table 1 displays, when the page **registered 25,343 impressions, 968 reactions, 21 comments, and 57 reposts**, the second year results demonstrate not only a quantitative increase but also enhanced qualitative engagement. This confirms that the expanded content strategy, including blog posts, webinars, cluster-related announcements, and targeted outreach, has effectively strengthened XR5.0’s digital footprint and visibility within the wider XR and AI innovation ecosystem.

Table 1-XR5.0 LinkedIn Metrics Comparison (Y1 vs. Y2)

Metric	Year 1	Year 2	Change
Followers	358	730	+372
Total Impressions	25,343	34,199	+8,856
Comments	21	43	+22
Reactions	968	1,138	+170

Table 2 displays some of the posts that gained more than 10% Click-Through Rate (CTR) (until the end of December 2nd 2025) during the project’s first year. An organic CTR above 10% on LinkedIn posts reflects a highly receptive audience and content that successfully resonates with targeted stakeholders.

Table 2-XR5.0 LinkedIn posts (M13-M24)

N0.	Link	Visual	CTR more than
1	https://tinyurl.com/5mvjh5ez		17.65%
2	https://tinyurl.com/2eabjm6a		14.2%
3	https://tinyurl.com/2hyd4umf		13.82%

4	https://tinyurl.com/bdhyp9ff		11.74%
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3.2.3 X

During the second year of the project, the XR5.0 account on X continued to grow steadily, further strengthening its presence within the wider XR and AI ecosystem. As of the day writing this deliverable (December 4th, 2025), the account counts **169 followers**, marking a strong increase compared to the previous year, as Table 3 displays. **348 posts** have been shared on the platform since its creation, including reposts, as Figure 12 displays.

Table 3-XR5.0 X Metrics Comparison (Y1 vs. Y2)

Metric	Year 1	Year 2
Followers	34	169
Following	n/a	557
Total posts	184 (incl retweets)	348

The content planning on X follows the same structure established for LinkedIn (see Figure 13), maintaining a regular posting rhythm aligned with the project’s KPI of at least three posts per month. However, this channel places a stronger emphasis on reposts (see Figure 14) leveraging X’s fast-paced and highly interactive environment. By frequently amplifying content published by partners, EU-funded initiatives, and projects within the BeyondXR cluster, the XR5.0 account enhances visibility while reinforcing its connections within the XR innovation community. This repost-centric approach has proven effective in broadening reach and strengthening relationships with relevant stakeholders, while helping XR5.0 stay aligned with current discussions, technological developments, and emerging trends in XR, AI, and Industry 5.0 applications. In addition, the account actively follows similar initiatives and organisations, enabling ongoing engagement, knowledge exchange, and identification of collaboration opportunities.

All original posts published on X are adapted to the platform’s concise style, ensuring consistency with XR5.0’s communication identity while meeting the expectations and interaction patterns typical of this channel.

Figure 12-X project’s account.

Figure 13-Sample XR5.0 posts on the X platform.

Figure 14-Sample repost of an XR5.0 post.

3.2.4 Facebook

XR5.0 continued to maintain an active, yet secondary presence on Facebook, in alignment with the overall social media strategy envisaged in the DoA. Although Facebook is not considered one of the project’s primary dissemination channels, it remains a complementary platform that supports the visibility and outreach achieved through LinkedIn and X (see Figure 15). Facebook provides an accessible entry point for broader public visibility, ensuring that project news, visual material, and updates remain discoverable across diverse user groups. The channel’s role will remain supplementary in order to support the project’s

multi-platform dissemination strategy and to ensure consistent messaging across all communication touchpoints.

Figure 15-XR5.0 Facebook Account.

3.2.5 YouTube

Building upon the foundations established in its first year, the XR5.0 YouTube channel continued to expand its role as a core component of the project’s dissemination and communication strategy. Throughout the second year, additional video material was produced and uploaded, enriching the channel with a broader range of content. This includes recordings from project webinars, presentations delivered at conferences, and visual summaries of consortium activities, all designed to provide stakeholders with accessible insights into the project’s progress.

Specific playlists have been created to organise the XR5.0 YouTube content more effectively, including dedicated sections such as “Pilot Videos,” “BeyondXR Webinars,” and “General Assembly Videos.” These playlists support easier navigation for stakeholders and ensure that all video material is categorised according to its purpose and audience.

By the end of the project’s second year, a total of **19 videos** had been uploaded to the XR5.0 YouTube channel, well above the project’s KPI of publishing **at least 10 videos** by the end of the project (see Figure 16). Note that YouTube serves as the main repository for the project’s videos, which are used in the scope of the project’s content/posts for other digital channels. The project’s strategy is to drive users to YouTube via other digital channel (e.g., LinkedIn) rather than creating a large base of YouTube (organic) subscribers to the XR5.0 channel.

Figure 16-XR5.0 YouTube Account.

3.3 Newsletters

Newsletters continue to play a central role in raising awareness and regularly informing the XR5.0 mailing list about the project’s progress. They provide stakeholders with timely updates on new blog posts, upcoming events, synergies within the XR ecosystem, and significant project milestones. To support their

visibility, the XR5.0 website continues to feature a dedicated sign-up banner, while an additional subscription prompt in the website footer ensures easy access for new users at any time. Complementary promotional posts on social media (see Figure 17) further reinforce the outreach of each newsletter edition by encouraging stakeholders to subscribe.

Figure 17-Social Media posts for new Newsletter subscribers.

In the second year, the visual identity of the newsletters has remained consistent, maintaining a clear and recognisable design aligned with the project’s branding guidelines. The content was expanded to reflect the increased activity of the consortium, incorporating updates on webinars, clustering actions, scientific achievements, and new collaborations within the BeyondXR network.

Throughout Year 2, XR5.0 produced **four additional newsletters**, bringing the total mailing list to **136 subscribers**. This demonstrates a steady growth of engaged stakeholders and exceeds the KPI target of producing four newsletters within this timeframe.

Table 4 below summarises the newsletters released during the second year. As indicated by the performance metrics, **the 7th newsletter**, which highlighted major achievements and developments within the XR cluster community, achieved the highest click-through performance, indicating strong engagement from the audience.

Table 4-XR5.0 Newsletters Produced and Dispatched during the Reporting Period (Jan-Dec 2025).

NL - Date	Newsletters Interface	Link	Successful Deliveries	Clicks per Unique Opens
5th January 14, 2025		Click for the 5th Newsletter	122	9,1%

<p>6th- May 13, 2025</p>		<p>Click for the 6th Newsletter</p>	<p>126</p>	<p>33.3%</p>
<p>7th - July 14, 2025</p>		<p>Click for the 7th Newsletter</p>	<p>130</p>	<p>35.9%</p>
<p>8th - December 5, 2025</p>		<p>Click for the 8th Newsletter</p>	<p>132</p>	<p>32.6%</p>

3.4 Published Blog Posts

Throughout the second year of implementation, XR5.0 continued to prioritise the production of high-quality, informative, and engaging blog content as a core component of its communication strategy. All partners remained actively involved in authoring and contributing to blog posts, which are published on the project website and disseminated across XR5.0’s social media channels and newsletters. This consistent output has significantly strengthened the project’s online presence and visibility, while also offering partners a platform to showcase their work, share technical insights, and highlight their individual contributions to the project’s progress. The Blog section recorded **657 sessions** on the official website in the second year of the project, indicating 657 distinct visit periods during which users engaged with one or more blog posts.

A total of **twenty-five (25) blog posts** were released throughout the second year, generating significant interest with thousands of views and impressions across the project’s digital channels. Annex I provides a detailed list of all published blog posts, reflecting the coordinated and continuous effort of the consortium to communicate developments and results in a structured and accessible manner.

Looking ahead, the project is planning the creation of **an edited booklet featuring a curated selection of the most impactful and insightful blog posts**. This book is expected to be developed by the middle of the project’s third year in order to serve as a consolidated knowledge resource that will integrate the most engaging blog posts of the project. This booklet is expected to further amplify the dissemination of XR5.0’s achievements and to boost the project’s “thought leadership” within the European XR and Industry 5.0 communities.

3.5 Projects Announcements – Local Level Dissemination

Throughout the second year, XR5.0 continued to strengthen its dissemination footprint by promoting key project milestones across various digital channels and partner networks. In addition to the announcements published on the project’s official website, several noteworthy mentions were featured on external platforms, further extending the project’s visibility within the wider XR community. As presented in Annex II, XR5.0 appeared in prominent cluster-level communication channels, including the MASTER XR, SPIRIT, and OpenVerse websites. XR5.0 published targeted content in these websites towards highlighting major updates and collaborative activities undertaken within 2025.

Moreover, partner organisations continued to support dissemination at the regional level. For instance, one of XR5.0’s Swiss partners was featured in a local newspaper, which provided additional exposure within the Swiss innovation landscape. Similar to the approach followed during the project’s first year, these regional announcements were used as a vehicle to broaden the project’s outreach by engaging local communities, industry stakeholders, and research networks in their respective countries.

This cross-promotion contributed to raising awareness of XR5.0 beyond its immediate audience and reinforced the project’s presence within the broader European XR and Industry 5.0 ecosystem. It also helped to enhance the recognition of the XR5.0 brand, to increase the project’s website traffic, and overall to reinforce the project’s credibility.

3.6 Future Planning (M25-M36) (January 2026-December 2026)

Table 5 below outlines the project’s plan to achieve and, where possible, exceed the dissemination/communication KPIs defined in the DoA about dissemination in social and electronic channels. This plan includes a range of activities, including regular social media updates, website enhancements, newsletters, blog posts featuring content provided by partners, as well as the development of whitepapers and press releases.

Table 5-Planning of Dissemination and Communication Activities for M25-M36.

DoA KPIs for the 3 rd Year	Planning for the 3 rd Year
- Web/social content, blogposts, articles, whitepapers: >4/month -Videos, YouTube channel: total in three years 1 promo/UC/tool, total >=10	-Social Media content: 5-6/month -Blogposts on website: 3-4/month -Videos, YouTube channel: 6-8 videos
Press releases, newsletters, and digital briefs Y3: >=10 (1/UC + 1/tool)	-Newsletters: Y3: >=6 -7 -Every pilot will create a dedicate whitepaper which will summarize the offered solution and which will be typically published after the respective pilot webinar.

4. PUBLICATIONS, WORKSHOPS AND PILOT WEBINARS

4.1 Overview of Coordination Activities towards Publications and other Activities

During the second year of the project, the dissemination team continued to follow the structured communication strategy developed during the first year in order to expand awareness and strengthen the project’s visibility across stakeholder groups. Bi-weekly WP7 meetings remained a central coordination mechanism, which ensured continuous alignment between partners and the dissemination team, as well as regular engagement of all XR5.0 partners with the dissemination activities. These meetings focused on sharing updates on all dissemination, communication, and clustering activities, while also collecting input from partners regarding their planned actions, participation in events, upcoming publications, and other relevant dissemination/communication activities. Throughout the year, partners were actively encouraged to take part in relevant conferences, workshops, and webinars to maximise the project’s exposure and extend its outreach across scientific, industrial, and community audiences. In total, **18 WP7 meetings** (see Figure 18) were held during the second reporting period. Alongside communication updates, these meetings also included regular briefings on exploitation planning and emerging standardisation contributions to ensure a coherent and integrated approach across all WP7 tasks.

The second year of the project marked progress in organising Pilot Webinars, designed to showcase the technological advancements and industrial relevance of the XR5.0 pilots. While **six pilot-focused webinars are planned overall**, two of them were successfully conducted during the second year. The latter provided to stakeholders early insights into the project’s applied results and fostered engagement with industry practitioners.

Figure 18-Repository of 18 WP7 meetings.

4.2 Open Access Scientific Publications Y2

In the second year of the project, XR5.0 expanded its scientific and academic footprint, reflecting the maturation of technical outcomes and the increased engagement of partners in research dissemination. Over this period, **seven new scientific publications** (see Table 6) were produced across reputable international conferences and proceedings, bringing the project’s **total to thirteen**.

The emphasis on conference publications aligns with the project’s expected trajectory for scientific output, as the second year marks the phase where substantial technical results emerge from the pilots, system integration activities, and reference architecture developments. As a result, the consortium was able to present findings at venues such as **IEEE ICE/ITMC**, **DCOSS-IoT**, and **XR Salento**, positioning XR5.0 within the broader research discourse on human-centric XR and Industry 5.0 technologies.

All publications produced during this period follow the project’s Open Access policy and are available through the XR5.0 website and its dedicated Zenodo community as either Gold OA or Green OA

papers/publications. This ensures broad accessibility and long-term preservation, while at the same time supporting the project's commitment to open science and knowledge sharing.

Table 6-XR5.0 Scientific publications (M13-M24) (January 2025- December 2025).

NO.	Scientific Publications
1	<p>Conference Paper <i>Motion Trajectory Prediction in Dynamic Human-Robot Shared Workspaces.</i> Samuele, D., Cutrona, V., Montini, E., Matteri, D., Masiero, S., & Bettoni, A. (2025, May). Motion Trajectory Prediction in Dynamic Human-Robot Shared Workspaces. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15720093 <u>Contributing partner:</u> SUPSI</p>
2	<p>Conference Paper <i>A Protocol for Human-Centric Adaptive User Interfaces: From Static Interaction to Behaviour-Driven Adaptation.</i> Matteri, D., Masiero, S., Dell'Oca, S., Montini, E., Cutrona, V., & Canetta, L. (2025, June). In <i>2025 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC)</i> (pp. 1–10). IEEE. DOI:10.1109/ICE/ITMC65658.2025.11106653 <u>Contributing partner:</u> SUPSI</p>
3	<p>Conference Paper <i>A Scalable Data-Driven Methodology for Human Intention Prediction in Diverse Collaborative Scenarios.</i> Dell'Oca, S., Montini, E., Cutrona, V., Matteri, D., Landolfi, G., & Bettoni, A. (2025, June 23). Conference paper archived on Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15720280. <u>Contributing partner:</u> SUPSI</p>
4	<p>Conference Paper <i>Bridging Industrial Expertise and XR with LLM-Powered Conversational Agents.</i> Tomkou, D., Fatouros, G., Andreou, A., Makridis, G., Liarokapis, F., Dardanis, D., ... & Kyriazis, D. (2025). arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.05527. <u>Contributing partners:</u> INNOV, CYENS, UPRC</p>
5	<p>Conference Paper <i>Integrating Asset Administration Shell with an IIoT Platform for Human-Centric Digital Twins.</i> Almeida, B., Guedes, J., Ferreira, P., Di Orio, G., Matteri, D., Montini, E., ... & Maló, P. (2025, June). In <i>2025 21st International Conference on Distributed Computing in Smart Systems and the Internet of Things (DCOSS-IoT)</i> (pp. 01–08). IEEE. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16283191 <u>Contributing partner:</u> UNP</p>
6	<p>Conference Paper <i>Strengthening Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes using Extended Reality Applications in the Industry 5.0 Domain.</i> Mavrogiorgis, E., Tsanakas, S., Zafeiropoulos, N., & Papadakis, N. (2025). Conference paper archived on Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16284631. <u>Contributing partners:</u> SPACE, SYN</p>
7	<p>Conference Paper <i>XR Training in Industry 5.0: Advancing Human-Machine Collaboration with the XR5.0 Training Platform.</i> Oliveira, J., Saraiva, T., Shah, H. M., Mavrogiorgis, E., Mavrogiorgou, A., & Kiourtis, A. (2025, June). In <i>International Conference on Extended Reality (XR Salento 2025, LNCS)</i>. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-97769-5_7 <u>Contributing partners:</u> IML, UPRC</p>

4.3 Workshops, Webinars and Events

4.3.1 Overview of XR5.0 Participation in Workshops, Webinars and Events

Workshops, webinars, and public events continued to play a central role in fostering collaboration, supporting knowledge exchange, and showcasing the evolving results of the XR5.0 project during its second year. As the project entered a more mature phase, partners significantly increased their participation in scientific, industrial, and community-oriented events across Europe. These activities brought together project partners, domain experts, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and technology users, enabling targeted discussions, demonstrations, and dissemination of emerging project outcomes.

Throughout the second year of the project, XR5.0 partners were actively involved in a wide range of conferences, technical workshops, innovation forums, live demonstrations, and pilot-focused exhibitions. Table 7 summarises all workshops, conferences, demonstrations, and dissemination activities in which XR5.0 partners participated during the second year of the project.

Table 7-Partners' participations and contributions in workshops and other events Y2.

Date	Partner	Country	Explanation of dissemination activity
February 11, 2025	INNOV	Belgium	In person meeting with XR related projects financed under H2020 and Horizon Europe. Innov presented the XR5.0 Project in the event A2 Unit Brussels. Meeting with XR related projects financed under H2020 and Horizon Europe programmes.
February 20-21, 2025	SSF	Switzerland	The first-ever International Humanoid Forum was held on February 20-21 in Biel/Bienne. Over 30 speakers and 150 attendees from academia, industry, and politics gathered to discuss the future of humanoid robotics and its potential impact on society. The event received extensive media coverage, including RTS's 19:30 news and TeleBielingue, highlighting the growing interest in this cutting-edge technology. Read more in the relevant post, found in the XR5.0 website here .
March 5, 2025	GFT	Belgium	GFT Technologies (Matteo Falsetta – Project Coordinator of the XR5.0 Project) participated in HSbooster.eu Final Event: Impact through Research, Innovation and Standards. Read more in the relevant post, found in the XR5.0 website.
May 13, 2025	LNS	Switzerland	The Zurich AI Conference 2025 May 13 2025 from 18:00 to 22:00 (CET).
May 8-9, 2025	HOLO	Germany	HOLO actively participated as an exhibitor at the XR EXPO 2025, held in Stuttgart from May 8 to May 9. During the event, HOLO showcased its XR products and solutions – Hololight Hub, Hololight Stream and Hololight Space, drawing interest from both industry professionals and academic researchers. Read more in the relevant post, found in the XR5.0 web site.
June 11-13, 2025	SSF	Switzerland	6th International Smart Factory Summit, taking place on June 11-13 in Biel/Bienne, Switzerland. Co-organized by UNIDO, this year's event focuses on "Deep Tech Smart Factory: Uniting Humans, AI, Robots and Processes", exploring emerging technologies and their economic and societal impacts on manufacturing.

June 12, 2025	INNOV, UNP	Italy	<p>Insightful discussions and cutting-edge research took centre stage in Lucca, Italy, during the IEEE DCOSS 2005 – TI-2025 workshop on June 12th, 2025</p> <p>Innov-acts presented a paper on trusted and human-centred approaches for industrial training based on extended reality technologies leveraging an LLM server developed in the XR5.0 Project.</p>
June 13, 2025	ATB	Germany	<p>Presentation of the XR5.0's first results and current activities to one of ATB's interest groups; 13/06/2025; Around 10 persons attended the workshop.</p>
July 15-18, 2025	UBI	Croatia	<p>The XR5.0 paper titled “Human-Centric AI-Enabled Extended Reality Reference Architecture for Industry 5.0” was successfully presented at the 11th International Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies (CoDIT 2025), held from July 15–18 in Split, Croatia. Read more in the relevant post.</p>
October 2025	SSF, LNS, realwear	Switzerland	<p>Article in the local newspaper Bieler Tagblatt shed light on the innovative use and development of Augmented Reality (AR) glasses by XR5.0 partners in Switzerland. The publication explores how digitalisation is empowering companies to enhance their operations and improve customer satisfaction through smart, connected solutions. Read more in the relevant post in the XR5.0 web site.</p>
November 5, 2025	SPACE	Greece	<p>A live demo session showcasing Pilot 5 of the XR5.0 project, named “Increased Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes”, was completed, with 10 participants attending this demonstration in Athens, Greece. Read more in the relevant post in the XR5.0 web site.</p>
November 10th, 2025	SPACE, SYN	Greece	<p>On November 10th–12th, 2025, SPACE HELLAS, in cooperation with SYNELIXIS, participated in the IEEE Conference on NFV/SDN with the demo paper titled “Strengthening Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes Using Extended Reality Applications in the Industry 5.0 Domain”, in Athens, Greece. Read more in the relevant post in the XR5.0 web site.</p>
November 4th 2025	INNOV	Online	<p>XR5.0 is committed to follow and contribute to the activities of the newly established Virtual Worlds Association. The project participated in the on-line event of the The Virtual and Augmented Reality Industrial Coalition, where the establishment of the Virtual Worlds Association was presented. XR5.0 joined also the discuss of the standardisation working group.</p>
November 2025	UPRC	Belgium	<p>The University of Piraeus is a member of the European Security and Defence College (ESDC). ESDC holds its Annual Training and Education Conference (ATEC) in Brussels in which UPRC shared some information regarding XR5.0's Training Platform and its benefits in combining Immersive environments and AI.</p>
December 10, 2025	UPRC	online	<p>OpenVerse CSA a workshop to bring projects on technologies around XR + AI, AIoT and IoT.</p>
December 12, 2025	ATB		<p>Presentation of the XR5.0's early prototypes in Pilot 1 to one of ATB's interest groups. Around 10 persons attended the workshop.</p>

December 15, 2025	INNOV	online	Presentation of XR5.0 Commercialisation Blueprints and Business Models linked to XR5.0 pilots to a “Commercialisation Training” online Workshop organized for the Doctoral Candidates of the Horizon Europe Marie Curie AGORA project (Doctoral Network)
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4.3.2 Participation in the Virtual Worlds Association

XR5.0 has also strengthened its engagement with broader European initiatives by joining the newly established [Virtual Worlds Association](#), an alliance bringing together key stakeholders in Virtual and Extended Reality, including standardisation bodies, policymakers, regulators, and EU-funded projects. The Association aims to promote open, human-centric virtual world technologies and support their adoption across sectors such as industry, education, healthcare, and culture. In this context, XR5.0, intends to participate and contribute in selected working subgroups, including one dedicated to standardisation activities. During these sessions, the project will present its work on industrial architectures, developed in collaboration with the XR2Industry project. Moreover it will contribute to the Association’s ongoing technical and policy discussions.

4.4 Pilot Webinars and Face to Face Trainings

As the project entered a more advanced stage and the pilot activities progressed, the dissemination team, in close collaboration with the pilot partners, initiated the development of a **dedicated series of six webinars, one for each pilot**, to further enhance visibility and facilitate knowledge sharing across the XR5.0 community. Five of these sessions are planned as online webinars, while one will take place as an in-person training event, two of them took place in the reporting period (see Figure 19).

The purpose of this pilot-focused series is fourfold: to disseminate the XR5.0 pilot applications, to obtain interactive feedback through live surveys, to support the continuous growth of the XR5.0 ecosystem, and to contribute directly to the achievement of the project’s dissemination KPIs, particularly those related to online and face-to-face training activities, live audience engagement, and feedback collection.

To ensure a coherent and impactful structure, each webinar has been designed with an approximate duration of 25–35 minutes and follows a consistent format comprising a focused presentation of the relevant Use Case(s), an interactive Q&A session, and a short live survey consisting of 5–8 targeted questions aimed at gathering meaningful insights from participants. All sessions are recorded and subsequently made available on the XR5.0 YouTube channel, the project’s social media platforms, and the official website, supporting broader accessibility and long-term dissemination of pilot results. This structured approach enables XR5.0 to enhance its visibility, encourage stakeholder interaction, and collect measurable feedback aligned with the project’s Description of Action, thus reinforcing the role of the pilot webinars as a key component of the project’s communication and stakeholder engagement strategy.

4.4.1 1st Pilot 1 Webinar: “XR and AI-Enhanced Robotics Training”

On 9 December 2025, the Pilot 1 webinar titled “XR and AI-Enhanced Robotics Training” was held online as part of the dedicated pilot-focused dissemination series. The session attracted 32 registrations, with 16 participants attending, representing a mix of industrial stakeholders, technology experts, and research partners. The webinar provided an in-depth presentation of the XR5.0 training solutions developed under Pilot 1, highlighting how XR and AI technologies can enhance robotics training processes in industrial environments. To encourage engagement, the session incorporated a live survey to collect real-time feedback from attendees, followed by an open discussion and Q&A segment, allowing participants to engage directly with the speakers.

4.4.2 2nd Pilot 6 Webinar: “F2F Training Session at the SSF: Project & Pilot Presentation and Hands-On Demonstration”

During the second year of the project, **two out of the six pilot-focused sessions were successfully delivered**. Notably, on 18 November 2025, Pilot 6 organised the “F2F Training Session at the SSF: Project

& Pilot Presentation and Hands-On Demonstration”, hosted at the Swiss Smart Factory (SSF) within the Switzerland Innovation Park Biel/Bienne. This session featured an in-depth presentation of the XR5.0 project, an overview of Pilot 6 objectives and technologies, and interactive demonstrations with the participating companies. The sessions offered attendees a practical understanding of the pilot’s human-centric XR solutions and their application within real industrial environments. All materials related to the Pilot webinars, including the agenda, presentations, and recording, are available though the XR5.0 project website.

Figure 19-Pilot 1 Webinar Agenda, Pilot 6 F2F Training Agenda.

4.5 Future Planning (M25-M36) (January 2026-December 2026)

Four additional pilot webinars are scheduled to take place during the final phase of the project, further supporting the structured dissemination strategy established for the pilot series. These upcoming sessions will enable partners to present the technical progress, training methodologies, and human-centric XR solutions developed within each pilot, while continuing to engage stakeholders from industry, research, and vocational training communities.

Two of these webinars have already been officially announced through the XR5.0 communication channels (see Figure 20). The first, titled **“XR5.0 Technologies for Worker-Centric Aircraft Maintenance Training,”** will take place on 19 February 2026 at 10:00 CET and will feature presentations from TAP, IML, and SUPSI partners. The second announced session, **“Enhancing Technician Training & Remote Support in Industry 5.0 with XR and AI: Insights from XR5.0 Pilot 5,”** is scheduled for 20 March 2026 at 11:00–11:30 CET, with contributions from SYN and SPACE. Both webinars highlight practical implementations of XR and AI technologies within real industrial settings and illustrate how the XR5.0 pilots enable safer, more efficient, and more personalised training processes.

Figure 20-Upcoming Pilot Webinars.

Table 8 below presents the scientific publications (journals and conferences) planned by the XR5.0 partners for the upcoming reporting period. As the project enters the most advanced phase, these planned activities reflect the growing availability of mature technical results and the consortium’s strengthened engagement with the scientific community. While this table provides an indicative overview of the envisaged publication, adjustments to venues, timelines, and thematic focus may be required to align with evolving project outcomes and conference opportunities. Hence, this table is currently indicative, but subject to changes in terms of additional or alternative conference venues and targeted journals Any updates or modifications to this plan will be reported in the final release of the dissemination and communication deliverable (D7.4).

Table 8-XR5.0 Plan for Scientific Journal and Conferences Publications (M25-M36) (List of Venues and Journals Subject to Changes and Updated During the Third Year of the Project).

Dates	Type of Publications	Publication Description	Partner
2026	Journal Publication	IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics	UPRC
2026	Journal Publication	Information (MDPI) — Special Issue: Extended Reality and Its Applications	UPRC
2026	Journal Publication	IEEE Access	CYENS
2026	Journal Publication	Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)	IML
2026	Journal Publication	Perspectives in Law, Business and Innovation (Springer)	COR
2026	Journal Publication	Springer VR/ IEEE Access	SYN
2026	Journal Publication	Computers in human behavior - Elsevier	IPIA
2026	Journal Publication	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	IPIA
21-25/03/2026	Scientific Conference	IEEE VR 2026	UPRC
16-20/06/2026	Scientific Conference	XR Salento 2026	UPRC
17-19/06/2026	Scientific Conference	XRM 2026	UPRC
23-26/06 2026	Scientific Conference	MED'26 (The 34th Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation)	UBI
2027	Scientific Conference	International Italia NODIG	EKSO
16-20/06/2026	Scientific Conference	XR Salento 2026	SPACE
16-19/07/2026	Scientific Conference	AIAI 2026	SPACE

16-20/06/2026	Scientific Conference	XR Salento 2026	SUPSI
TBD	Scientific Conference	APMS 2026	SUPSI
16-20/06/2026	Scientific Conference	XR Salento 2026	SYN
16-19/07/2026	Scientific Conference	AIAI 2026	SYN
22-24/06/2026	Scientific Conference	DCOSS-IoT 2026	UNP
22-24/06/2026	Scientific Conference	DCOSS-IoT 2026	INNOV

Lists of relevant conferences that offer suitable publication opportunities for XR5.0 are regularly circulated among all partners. In addition, the partners receive targeted notifications highlighting specific opportunities that align with their technical focus and ongoing research activities towards ensuring that each team is supported in identifying the most appropriate venues for disseminating their results.

The development of an edited **Open Access book** featuring contributions from the **BeyondXR cluster** is currently under consideration as a joint dissemination initiative with other projects/contributors of the cluster. XR5.0 is willing to act as the book's lead editor. The implementation of this initiative is however subject to the confirmation of the BeyondXR projects to contribute chapters to the book. Specifically, to advance this effort, the XR5.0 team plans to consult cluster members to assess their interest in contributing individual chapters that reflect the outcomes, methodologies, and thematic expertise of each participating project. Pending a sufficient number of confirmed expressions of interest (i.e., estimated at 15–16 chapters across the cluster) the XR5.0 team will prepare and submit a formal book proposal to an appropriate/reputable academic publisher. Open Access publishing will be pursued to provide free and unlimited access to the book's contents in-line with FAIR and OA practices.

5. THE BEYOND XR PROJECTS CLUSTER: AN INITIATIVE WITH XR5.0 IN A LEADING ROLE AND XR2INDUSTRY COLLABORATION

5.1 Overview of BeyondXR Purpose, Organization and Digital Channels – XR5.0 Inputs

In the second year of the project, the XR5.0 consortium continued to strengthen and expand the collaborative ecosystem initiated in the first year. Building upon the early efforts to connect with projects working on Extended Reality and emerging technologies, the cluster matured into a formally branded initiative now known as **BeyondXR**. The name was selected collectively during the second project year, reflecting the cluster’s aim to establish a strong, recognisable identity and to promote a unified presence within the broader XR community.

BeyondXR brings together **thirteen Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects** that collectively explore the integration of XR, AI, robotics, immersive media, and next-generation learning technologies. The overall objective of the cluster is to foster synergies, coordinate dissemination efforts, promote cross-sector innovation, and amplify the societal and technological impact of the participating projects.

XR5.0 maintains a leading role within the cluster’s activities. Throughout the second year, monthly meetings were held to plan joint events, coordinate communication efforts, organise cross-project webinars, and exchange recommendations that strengthen each project’s individual and collective dissemination impact. These collaborative actions will be further detailed in subsequent chapters of this deliverable.

To reinforce knowledge exchange and community building, the cluster actively uses **the XR2Learn Platform/Forum** (see Figure 21) as a shared digital space. XR5.0 contributes regularly by uploading project news, webinar announcements, and relevant updates to ensure consistent communication across the broader XR stakeholder community. A sample of such posts is illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 21-XR2Learn Platform/ Forum.

Figure 22-XR5.0 news on the XR2Learn Platform.

Also, the BeyondXR cluster manages a dedicated **LinkedIn Group** (see Figure 23) that has grown to approximately **405 active members**. This group functions as a central hub for discussions, cross-project promotion, and the dissemination of activities related to XR, AI, and immersive technologies. The group’s continuous growth illustrates the increasing interest of industry professionals, researchers, and practitioners in the themes explored by the cluster.

Figure 23-LinkedIn Group - BeyondXR.

5.2 Participating Projects

The BeyondXR cluster continued to expand throughout the project’s second year and now consists of **thirteen actively engaged EU-funded projects**. During this period, **three additional projects** joined the cluster, further strengthening its multidisciplinary character and widening the scope of XR-related collaboration. The XR5.0 website hosts a dedicated section that presents all participating BeyondXR projects in a clear and structured manner, ensuring full visibility and easy access for stakeholders.

Table 9 below summarises the three (3) projects that joined the cluster during the second year, while the ten projects already participating in the first year have been thoroughly presented in the previous deliverable.

Table 9-BeyondXR cluster projects that Joined During Y2 of XR5.0 Lifetime.

XR Cluster

TRANSMIXR (<https://transmixr.eu/>) aims to ignite the immersive media sector by enabling new narrative visions through the development and adoption of Extended Reality (XR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies. The project focuses on advancing social XR and AI technologies for application within media production, delivery, and consumption, targeting the creative and cultural sectors.

SERMAS (<https://sermasproject.eu/>) lays the foundations of next-generation XR systems, looking at how people relate and interact with the technology. Transform your Extended Reality (XR) experience with SERMAS. Embrace social acceptance and discover our concepts, techniques, and tools that will help you discover the full potential of XR systems through coherent design, implementation, and deployment.

SPITIT (<https://spirit-project.eu/>) telepresence represents the next generation of communication applications that will significantly improve immersive experiences in both human-to-human and human-to-machine interactions by blurring the physical and virtual worlds. While this is already influencing how we work, it will have an even greater impact in the future, contributing to increased resilience to environmental disruptions, industry productivity, and energy efficiency. Due to their complexity, cost, data compression, and bandwidth requirements, these solutions have not been scaled yet. SPIRIT, which is funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe programme, researches, develops, and demonstrates low-latency and scalable solutions that will ultimately bring real-time immersive telepresence into practice.

5.3 Joint Meetings of BeyondXR Cluster

During the second year of the project, collaboration within the BeyondXR cluster evolved significantly, building upon the structured coordination mechanisms established during the first year. Monthly meetings continued to serve as the primary channel for aligning activities, exchanging updates, and planning collective dissemination actions across all participating XR-focused EU projects. These meetings remain central to ensuring cohesion, enabling partners to identify synergies, coordinate communication efforts, and collectively promote the cluster's technological and scientific advancements. As presented in Annex III, the monthly sessions brought together an expanded group of thirteen active projects, reflecting the cluster's growth and increased relevance within the European XR ecosystem.

Discussions throughout the year focused on a broad spectrum of joint actions, such as harmonising cross-marketing strategies, creating shared visual identities and templates, synchronising social media campaigns, and developing unified messaging to enhance the visibility of the cluster as a whole. Particular emphasis was placed on promoting key events, open calls, and scientific outputs, ensuring that each project benefits from the collective outreach capacity of the network.

In parallel, a major focus of this year's collaboration involved strengthening the cluster's branding and shared identity. A dedicated effort was undertaken to define the BeyondXR name, refine its visuals, and enhance its presence across communication channels. The meetings also served as a planning space for joint events. Several collaborative webinars were organised during the second year, bringing together experts from multiple projects to address emerging topics. These webinars have proven to be impactful activities that engage diverse audiences and increase the collective visibility of the BeyondXR cluster.

To support these coordinated efforts, a shared repository continues to operate as an organisational hub, containing templates, meeting notes, promotional materials, and presentation resources needed for joint dissemination activities.

5.4 Joint Webinars

In the second year of the project, **three additional joint webinars** were organised by the XR5.0 dissemination team in collaboration with the BeyondXR cluster, among various other events/webinars organized or co-organized by cluster members. These three webinars were led by XR5.0 based on the project's leading role in the cluster. Basic information about the webinars is included in Table 10, while their detailed agendas are provided in ANNEX IV. The webinars achieved considerable attendance. Note that their scope included legal, regulatory compliance and standardization themes, which complemented other webinars of the cluster that focused mainly on the technical/technological results of the various projects.

5.4.1 3rd Webinar: “Legal Issues in Extended Reality: Balancing Innovation with Regulation”

On 27 January 2025, from 10:00 to 11:00 CET, the third joint webinar titled “Legal Issues in Extended Reality: Balancing Innovation with Regulation” (see Figure 24), brought together experts and stakeholders to explore the rapidly evolving legal and ethical landscape surrounding XR technologies. The event, organised by the XR5.0 project in collaboration with the BeyondXR cluster, attracted 52 registered participants and 50 attendees joining the live session. The webinar featured distinguished speakers who presented key regulatory, compliance, and ethical considerations associated with the development and deployment of XR solutions. Their contributions provided attendees with a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities emerging at the intersection of policy, technology, and innovation. Presenters shared practical insights and research findings, offering valuable perspectives on data protection, safety frameworks, intellectual property, and governance models relevant to XR systems.

The session concluded with an interactive open discussion, during which participants engaged directly with the experts, raised questions, and explored future trends shaping the regulatory framework of immersive technologies.

Detailed information about the 3rd webinar, including the agenda, the presentations and the recording of the event can be found on the XR5.0 project website at: <https://xr50.eu/news/3rd-webinar-of-xr-projects-cluster-legal-issues-in-extended-reality-balancing-innovation-with-regulation-2/>

Figure 24-Social Media post of the 3rd BeyondXR Clusters' webinar.

5.4.2 4th Webinar: “Human-Centric Technologies and Applications for the Future of Extended Reality”

On March 20th, 2025, from 13:00 to 14:30 CET, the BeyondXR Cluster hosted its fourth joint webinar, titled “Human-Centric Technologies and Applications for the Future of Extended Reality,” (see Figure 25). The event explored the evolving role of adaptive and user-centred technologies in shaping next-generation XR applications across education, culture, and industrial environments. A total of 67 participants registered, and 40 individuals attended the webinar, engaging actively in the discussions that followed the presentations. The session brought together experts from various projects within the BeyondXR Cluster, who presented their latest research and solutions focused on human-centred XR innovation. Speakers highlighted emerging challenges, future technological directions, and the societal impact of XR systems designed with user experience, accessibility, and cognitive support at their core. Their contributions offered attendees a comprehensive understanding of how human-centric design principles can drive meaningful advancements across different sectors. Following the presentations, an open discussion provided participants with the opportunity to interact directly with the experts, exchange perspectives, and explore the implications of XR adoption in real-world contexts.

Detailed information about the 4th webinar, including the agenda, the presentations and the recording of the event, can be found on the XR5.0 project website at: <https://xr50.eu/news/4th-webinar-of-xr-projects-cluster-human-centric-technologies-and-applications-for-the-future-of-extended-reality-2/>

Figure 25-Social Media post - Recording of the 4th BeyondXR Clusters' webinar.

5.4.3 5th Webinar: “Breaking Barriers: How Open XR Standards Unlock Interoperability and Compliance”

The fifth webinar of the BeyondXR Cluster, titled “Breaking Barriers: How Open XR Standards Unlock Interoperability and Compliance,” (see Figure 26), was held on July 14th, 2025, from 15:00 to 16:30 CET. The session brought together experts from leading initiatives to discuss the critical role of open XR standards in enabling interoperability, compliance, and seamless integration across the extended reality ecosystem. A total of 24 participants attended the event, matching the 24 registrations, and the presentations were followed by a productive discussion with active audience engagement. Organised by the XR5.0 project in collaboration with the BeyondXR Cluster, the webinar highlighted standards-related contributions from XR2Industry, the SPIRIT project, XR5.0, and XR4Europe. Speakers shared insights into emerging frameworks, practical implementation challenges, and the broader impact of open standards on fostering innovation and ensuring trustworthy and scalable XR solutions.

Detailed information about the 5th webinar, including the agenda, the presentations and the recording of the event, can be found on the XR5.0 project website at:

<https://xr50.eu/news/5th-webinar-of-beyondxr-cluster-breaking-barriers-how-open-xr-standards-unlock-interoperability-and-compliance-2/>

Figure 26-Social Media post - Recording of the 5th BeyondXR Clusters’ webinar.

Table 10-Overview Information about the three new Joint webinars of the BeyondXR Cluster.

Webinar/ Date	Registered Participants	Actual Attendees	Audience Profiles
<i>“Legal Issues in Extended Reality: Balancing Innovation with Regulation”</i> January 27th, 2025, from 10:00 to 11:00 CET	52	50	XR/AI Researchers; Legal/LegalTech Professionals
<i>“Human-Centric Technologies and Applications for the Future of Extended Reality”</i> March 20, 2025, from 13:00 to 14:30 CET	67	40	XR/AI Researchers and Scientists; UI/UX Experts
<i>“Breaking Barriers: How Open XR Standards Unlock Interoperability and Compliance”</i> July 14, 2025, from 15:00 to 16:30 CET	24	24	XR/AI Researchers and Scientists; Standardization Experts

5.5 XR5.0 and XR2Industry Collaboration

XR5.0 has established a close collaboration with the XR2Industry project in order to explore shared objectives and potential synergies. Throughout the reporting period, the two projects held a series of joint technical discussions to exchange updates on system architectures, tools, pilot activities, and areas where integration may be beneficial. Building on these exchanges, **two joint workshops have been planned**, during which both projects will present key technological components, such as authoring tools, XR training solutions, and the Clawdite platform. This collaboration aims to identify complementarities across the projects’ approaches, particularly regarding tools, data management, and metadata practices, and to assess opportunities for alignment that could enhance the broader European XR ecosystem.

5.6 Future Planning (M25-M36) (January 2026- December 2026)

Looking ahead to the last period of the XR5.0 project, the dissemination team will continue to strengthen and expand the activities of the BeyondXR community. A priority for the coming months is to further grow the cluster by engaging additional XR-focused initiatives and fostering meaningful synergies with new and

ongoing European projects. As part of this strategy, additional joint webinars will be organized to support the projects in raising awareness about their most up to date results (as of 2026). For each session, the dissemination team will collaborate with participating projects to define themes, identify speakers, align schedules, and prepare the necessary promotional materials. Furthermore, the prospect of a joint XR5.0-led Open Access publication (book) is explored as outlined in previous sections. This falls under one of the the main objectives for the coming year, which is to produce joint publications that highlight cross-project research findings and shared perspectives on the future of XR technologies. These publications will help reinforce the cluster’s collective identity while demonstrating the value of coordinated European efforts in advancing XR innovation. Monthly meetings will continue to maintain the momentum of the community, as they are a regular space for project representatives to exchange updates, discuss ongoing dissemination actions, align on joint initiatives, and identify new opportunities for collaboration.

6. UPDATES ON THE XR5.0 STAKEHOLDERS DATABASE

During its second year, the XR5.0 project made substantial progress in expanding and refining its stakeholders’ database, further strengthening the project’s outreach across multiple sectors. As described in the previous deliverable, this database consolidates information gathered through various channels, including the project’s social media platforms (LinkedIn, X, YouTube, and Facebook), email distribution lists, webinar registrations, and additional targeted communication activities. Each entry includes the stakeholder’s name, email address, source platform, country, and professional category, allowing the consortium to better understand and engage with its community.

By the time this deliverable was prepared, the database had grown to more than **760 contacts**, marking an increase of nearly **300 new stakeholders** compared to the 475 recorded in the first project year. This considerable expansion exceeds the KPI target for Year 2, **which required a minimum of 500 entries**, demonstrating the project’s strengthened visibility, reach, and ability to attract interest from relevant communities. Among the **27 EU Member States, stakeholders from 24 countries** are represented in the XR5.0 database, in addition to entries from **the United Kingdom**. The only Member States not yet represented are **Latvia, Slovakia, and Poland**.

The twenty countries with the highest representation are illustrated in Figure 27. Greece is a leading contributor with 99 contacts, followed by India (23) and Germany (15). The database reflects a diverse mix of academic and industrial stakeholders active in domains related to XR technologies, immersive solutions, and digital innovation. The largest share of entries originates from the Technology and Software Development sector. In terms of professional roles, Chief Executive Officers, Founders, and Co-Founders form the largest group, followed by researchers and academic professionals. Significant representation is also observed among Business Development, Sales, and Key Account Management professionals, highlighting the project’s growing relevance beyond strictly technical audiences.

As shown in Figure 28, LinkedIn continues to be the primary channel for stakeholder acquisition, contributing 552 contacts, followed by the X platform (128 entries) and webinar registrations (87 contacts). This distribution confirms that professional networking platforms remain the most effective means of reaching and engaging with communities active in XR and technology-driven sectors.

All collected data is securely stored and managed in full compliance with GDPR regulations, ensuring that informed consent is obtained and that data collection follows the principles of data minimisation and lawful processing.

Figure 27-Top 20 Stakeholders’ Countries Registered in the Stakeholders’ database -Y2.

Figure 28-Channels through which entries of the Stakeholders' Database have been collected -Y2.

7. STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

7.1 Standardisation liaisons and methodology

XR5.0 partner TOG is responsible for leading standardisation liaisons and activities within the XR5.0 project. This task primarily focuses on standardisation, clustering, and policy-making activities related to the project. The work involves liaisons and participation with industrial associations (EFFRA, DAIRO, AIOTI), project clusters and initiatives (e.g., AI4Europe, AI4Manufacturing), national manufacturing initiatives (e.g., Platform Industrie 4.0, Productech, Industry 2025), as well as SDOs (IEEE, ISO, CEN/CENELEC, ETSI). The project aims at contributing insights into pre-normative activities based on whitepapers, presentations to meetings of the above-listed initiatives, as well as participation in joint meetings and workshops.

The XR5.0 project partners recognise the importance of standardisation as one of the cornerstones of the overall dissemination and exploitation strategy for XR5.0 aimed at achieving widespread take-up of project results for European I5.0 applications and services. The use of existing standards and activities to standardise project innovations will accelerate and amplify the exploitation of the project innovations by providing the following benefits:

- Wider dissemination of results – standards-setting organisations and communities surrounding standards have substantial participation from actors involved in related XR technologies – proposals by the XR5.0 partners to extend existing standards or introduce new standards represent well-focused dissemination actions towards industrial organisations, technology providers, and academia.
- Greater confidence by industry – organisations seeking to exploit the project’s XR systems development and personalisation technologies will have greater confidence in the project results if they are based on existing standards, and even more so when parts of the new project technologies are being adopted as new standards, as this conveys greater longevity and broader involvement by industry beyond the consortium partners, as well as a more transparent process for technology evolution.
- Interoperability of components – the publication of standards utilised in developing the XR5.0 solution and any proposed new standards provides the ability for third-parties that might develop XR-based applications and services to be incorporated within the XR5.0 ecosystem, providing additional benefits to XR application developers and opportunities for specialist component providers (e.g. augmented and virtual reality equipment vendors) to exploit the technologies developed in the project.
- Choice of technology suppliers for I5.0 stakeholders – the use of existing standards and the establishment of new standards based on the project technologies gives I5.0 stakeholders a greater choice of technology suppliers as other components can be easily incorporated into the XR5.0 framework for new applications and services, or other XR deployment environments beyond those validated in the project can be easily targeted, thereby avoiding lock-in to potentially proprietary technologies.

The use of standards and standardisation of project results therefore supports both the exploitation and dissemination strategies, and contributes towards achieving the industrial impacts targeted by the project. Standardisation liaisons and activities provide information about standards for use in the XR5.0 Reference Model, as well as knowledge of how XR5.0 aligns with European laws, acts, and directives (Table 11), especially in rapidly evolving technology areas such as AI and digital twins.

Table 11 – Standardisation liaisons and activities

Partners	Standards/Directive - Results Alignment	Contribution to XR5.0
CYENS, SUPSI	OpenXR i.e., Khronos Group open standard for access to VR/AR engines and devices including holographic devices and immersive VR devices	XR5.0 used OpenXR for access to XR assets and devices as part of the UCs
TOG, UNP	Augmented Reality Framework from the ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG ARF)	XR5.0 has considered the ISG ARF in the specification of the XR5.0-Reference Model
IPIA, TOG	XR Safety Initiative (XRSI) Standards	Used in the XR5.0 co-creation to ensure safety/security
GFT, TOG	JTC 1/SC 42, AI Architecture: Standardised Architecture for BigData and AI Systems	XR extensions to this architecture will be considered as part of the XR5.0 Reference Model specification through DAIRO
COR, GFT	AI Act / AI Regulation: Proposal for regulating AI systems, as put forward by the EP and the Council of Europe	XR5.0 systems were assessed against their compliance to the AI Act based on the level of their risk for the worker; Feedback from the risk assessment will be provided to policy makers
UPRC, INNOV	IEEE P2976 Standard (XAI): Standard specifying the properties of an XAI model	XR5.0 has considered this standard in the specification of requirements for the XAI models in the project
LXS, TOG	Open Standards for AI Model Interoperability: ONNX, OpenML, IEEE 2941-2021	XR5.0 has developed AI models based on these standards to facilitate their exchange, interoperability, and reuse across XR environments.
TOG, COR, IPIA	IEEE 7000 standards for ethical AI applications	XR5.0 has used IEEE 7000 based benchmarks

As contributions to extend existing standards and potentially propose new standards are expected to accelerate industry adoption of the XR5.0 person-centric and AI-based paradigm for XR applications, the consortium has established a methodology for the selection of standardisation targets that has been applied as the technology development and industry validation tasks continue to be undertaken in the project. The methodology is summarised in the following sections.

7.2 Standards body selection

Process characteristics of standards bodies and the nature of their outputs play an important role in selecting the organisation that best fits the standardisation targets for the project. Key characteristics that will play a decisive role in the selection of the standards bodies to be targeted for adopting the project results are as follows:

- The alignment of the standardisation goals of XR5.0 with the scope of the targeted organisation;
- The alignment of the methods, processes and principles applied by the targeted organisation with XR5.0 project objectives, as well as the standardisation results and impact being pursued;
- The lifespan of the XR5.0 project and the timing of deliverables with the agenda of the targeted standards organisation;
- The geographic scope of the impact XR5.0 is pursuing through its planned standardisation activities and targets;
- IPR rules and confidentiality policies of targeted standards bodies, as well as XR5.0 consortium partners’ requirements;
- Membership rules and procedures for standards bodies and the possibilities for XR5.0 partners’ input and proposals to be taken into account.

In cases where the project technologies intended for standardisation are extensions to existing standards, the first choice for the standards organisation or community to target becomes clear. However, in the mostly new technology areas developed within the project, significant consideration must be given in the selection of the standards organisation or community to be targeted.

7.2.1 Timing

Standardisation processes are largely market-driven and usually start when market actors have identified the need to initiate a process of capturing user, industrial or functional requirements for what is to become a new or an improved specification or standard. When putting forward project results for standardisation, it is important to ensure that the challenge or area addressed is actually on the agenda of the targeted standards body, and that there is sufficient critical mass among the target standards body's members to at least support if not contribute to the process of finalising the specification or reference technology from the XR5.0 project. If this is not the case, additional efforts to build consensus or engage constituents may be necessary. However, if there is a belief that this situation can be changed within a reasonable timeframe, it might be advisable for XR5.0 to explore alternative organizations that have agendas more aligned with the standardization objectives of the XR5.0 project.

7.2.2 Technology focus area

Finding the standards body best covering the scope of XR5.0 technologies may seem a relatively easy part of the selection process. Nevertheless, it can be complicated to point out a single organisation because in some cases several standards bodies are addressing the specific standardisation area being targeted. In particular, multiple initiatives are underway for standardisation of various aspects of AI and digital twins and many existing standards addressing virtual and augmented reality technologies. Consequently, it may be necessary to define in much more detail the specifics of the envisaged results, which may not always be possible in the early to middle stages of the project.

Project results may be relevant to several standards bodies, but project resources may not be sufficient to interface with all of them. The specific focus areas were selected after the first industry validations in the project were completed as this provides greater assurance that XR5.0 will be able to pursue its standardisation goals and the inputs collected from industrial partners can be used to motivate proposed adoption of project results as new industry standards.

7.2.3 Open standardisation processes

There are a number of commonalities between processes adopted by most organisations that have proven to be essential to conducting voluntary, open, and market-driven standardisation processes. The following criteria have therefore been established by XR5.0 in selecting the target standards bodies:

- Specifications or standards are essentially the result of consensus between parties involved, and participation of all relevant stakeholders should be sufficiently ensured, e.g. by validating draft specifications through a public review process;
- Standardisation activities are carried out through what are essentially public processes; although work may normally be done by expert committees, other interested parties should have the opportunity to become involved;
- Approved drafts of standards and specifications are formally ratified by the members of the standards organisation, and subsequently published;
- Standards produced by an organisation are available to all interested parties either free of charge, or licensable on FRaND³ terms;
- Interoperability between various implementations is verified, either as part of the standardisation process or through a process of self-certification, installed by the parties involved, and its maintenance is embedded in the evolutionary processes of the standard.

³ Fair, reasonable, and non-discriminatory

The final criteria of verification are often the most challenging as many standards organisations do not establish procedures for the verification of products as being conformant to their standards. However, as project partner TOG operates certification programmes for its own and many other standards organisations, a shortcoming in this area by a candidate standards organisation may not be grounds for disqualification as TOG has the ability to put in place a certification programme for new or extended standards based on XR5.0 project results.

7.2.4 Confidentiality and intellectual property

Standards organisations do not always have the same rules with respect to confidentiality and intellectual property rights (IPR). While there are organisations that require their members and/or participants to submit their contributions and technologies or specifications for free (i.e. without obligations for users of this technology to pay license fees), other organisations may work under an IPR regime offering their contributors opportunities for exploiting standardised technology through licensing. As part of the selection process, the IPR regime of the targeted standards organisations were considered by XR5.0 partners, as well as their confidentiality policies, to verify they are aligned with project partners' requirements.

7.2.5 Geographic focus areas

Generally speaking, XR5.0 is pursuing standardisation of results at a global level in support of the I5.0. This will maximise exposure of project innovations to industry and consequently widen dissemination opportunities. In addition, it will help to prevent competing regional standards from emerging, which may cause barriers to trade for European XR platform providers and equipment vendors. However, some specific criteria for pursuing standardisation targets at a regional level should also be considered:

- Taking specific national or regional legislative or product/services requirements into account;
- Project partners that are particularly well embedded in national or regional standardisation organisations or processes;
- Resources needed for national or regional standardisation processes can be considerably lower and can often influence broader European standards.

Regional and global standardisation systems in some technologies are complementary, and several standards bodies have arrangements in place for addressing this, for example, in the area of national and EU-level security standards. Nevertheless, cooperation and exchange between globally and regionally orientated standards organisations is mostly organised on an ad-hoc basis for many technology areas.

7.2.6 Membership of standards bodies

Most standards bodies offer their membership to a variety of organisations, encompassing individual companies, non-profit organisations, institutions, governmental bodies, etc. although some formal standards bodies restrict membership to nationally appointed representatives. Although research projects are usually not excluded from membership, there can be several reasons (e.g. the financial consequences, or the limitations of a project's lifespan) for not applying for membership as a project. There are also some standards organisations where membership is not strictly necessary for participating in at least part of the standardisation process, while taking part in the decision making process usually does require membership. Some alternatives in case direct membership is not feasible are identified as follows:

- Participate through the membership of one of the project's consortium partners;
- Apply for an observer status or temporary membership that is offered by some standards bodies or industry consortia;
- Utilise public events (e.g. seminars, conferences, etc.) and forums that are sometimes organised by standards organisations for making contributions;
- Submit results through other standards organisations that are able to participate in the activities of the specific standards body a project intends to target (e.g. TOG has cross-membership agreements with several other standards organisations).
- Some standards bodies are willing to establish low or unfunded partnerships with EU-funded projects where the envisaged research is closely aligned with the interests of the organisation.

Considerations concerning membership in terms of costs, required representation for discussions and consensus building, and ability to influence outcomes and decision-making have been included in the selection process of standards organisations to be targeted by the XR5.0 project.

7.3 Selected standards organisations and community targets

The XR5.0 consortium partners have applied the criterion described in Section 7.1 and selected three standardisation communities to further the objectives of the project of providing substantial benefit to European developers of XR-driven systems by taking actions towards establishing industry standards that accelerate the development and ensure interoperability XR systems and applications. Each is an established industry supported standards defining organisation, which also includes participation from academia and research. An overview description of each standardisation community target is provided in the following sections.

7.3.1 Architecture Forum

The Architecture Forum is comprised of more than 200 member organisations that develop and maintain the TOGAF standard, which is the de facto global standard Architecture Development Methodology for IT systems. The Forum regularly publishes updates to the standard and supporting materials and there are several workgroups that develop and improve the TOGAF Standard in line with the changing needs of industry and Architects. These provide new materials and maintain the ecosystem of existing documentation. There are over 100,000 IT Architects that have been certified to apply TOGAF within their organisation or as services providers to other organisations. The Architecture Forum includes an active working group for Agile Systems Architecture that has produced a range of materials showing how to apply the TOGAF Standard in an agile setting and is developing The Open Group has a working group that is specifically developing the Open Agile Architecture Standard. They have also published TOGAF-compliant Reference Architectures for specific industries to speed the process of designing new applications and to ensure interoperability. As an established standard for enterprise systems, TOGAF is undergoing an expansion in scope with the development of extensions as two add-ins to the standard to specifically address the nuances of architecting CPS and AI-driven systems.

7.3.2 ArchiMate Forum

The ArchiMate Forum has over 40 member organisations and is dedicated to advancing the open and independent ArchiMate modelling language for Enterprise Architecture. It facilitates collaboration amongst member organizations in further developing and supporting the evolution of the ArchiMate standard, which provides an open and independent modelling language designed to help enterprise architects describe, analyse, and visualize the relationships among business domains in an organized manner. It provides a comprehensive framework for modelling various aspects of an organization, including its processes, information systems, and technology infrastructure. This helps stakeholders effectively visualize and analyse the interrelationships among various business domains, ultimately enhancing communication and decision-making amongst technology developers and end-users. In addition to the ArchiMate standard the Forum also makes available to industry Archi, which is a free, open-source modelling tool specifically designed for creating models using the ArchiMate language. It serves as a powerful software application that helps enterprise architects visualize, analyse, and communicate their enterprise architecture frameworks effectively. There are also many other open source and commercial modelling tools that support the ArchiMate standard.

7.3.3 Digital Twin Consortium

The Digital Twin Consortium (DTC) brings together industry, government and academia to drive consistency in vocabulary, architecture, security and interoperability of digital twin technology, as well as awareness, adoption and development of digital twin technology. Through a collaborative partnership with industry, academia, and government expertise, DTC is dedicated to the overall development of digital twins.

The primary objective is to accelerate the market by propelling innovation and guiding outcomes for technology end-users. The DTC seeks to identify and fill gaps in technology development, drive interoperability through frameworks and open-source code, develop and advocate consistent best-practice methodologies, and to advance scientific and technical research to expand the market. The DTC is part of the Object Management Group and its members are committed to using digital twins in their global operations and supply chains. TOG has been a longstanding member of OMG (and vice versa) having collaborated with OMG on multiple industry standardisation and certification initiatives over more than twenty years.

7.4 Standardisation Actions

7.4.1 Standardisation Action Steps

The XR5.0 project has established a set of common steps to be taken by the project partners towards achieving the standardisation of project results. The timing and specific actions to be taken will vary depending on the project technology, its maturity, and the standardisation community being targeted. The steps towards standardisation for each project technology are the following:

- **Submission preparation** – preparing the XR5.0 research and development results as a specification or proposal suitable for submission to the standards body or community to support the process of industry review and comment.
- **Constituency building** – partners identify various influential constituencies that will have an opinion or position with regard to the XR5.0 submission and will liaise them to understand their interests and positions and to solicit their support.
- **Consensus building** – organising meetings and briefings with those individuals or organisations that are important for the decision-making within a standards organisation or community.
- **Conflict resolution** – addressing questions, challenges, and alternative approaches from others outside the project consortium concerning the XR5.0 submission that has been forwarded to the targeted standards organisation or community for review and comment.
- **Acceptance** – the action by the standards community of recognising the XR5.0 specification as being an extension to an existing portfolio of specifications and technologies, or as a new industry reference standard.

During the development and industrial evaluations tasks within the project, specific candidate technologies have been considered, selected and targeted for standardisation. An initial set of candidates had been identified in the early project months, which was further refined based on the first industrial Pilot evaluations for the six application domains targeted by the project, along with the feedback and experience gained from the industrial deployments and usage.

Each of the selected technologies will progress through each of the standardisation steps through actions taken by the project partners. Some of the steps may not be completed until after the project is finalised due either to the maturity of the project results, or the time required by the targeted standards body or community to complete their required procedures.

7.4.2 Coordination of standardisation actions

The XR5.0 consortium includes a standards organisation as Task Leader for the standardisation activities in the project that provides overall coordination of the standardisation steps for each of the XR5.0 technologies targeted for standardisation. The Open Group already publishes platform, development tools, and other technology standards that have completed an industry consensus process. The Open Group also collaborates with many other standards organisations including cross-membership agreements with OMG and W3C, joint initiatives with ETSI and CEN/CENELEC supporting standardisation of EC funded research results, chairmanship and participation in several ISO Working Groups, and hosting and provision of the operational infrastructure for other independent standards groupings.

The core elements of the coordination strategy that is being utilised within XR5.0 to establish the actions needed for standardisation of results are the following:

1. Periodic reviews at major development milestones in the work plan are carried out to identify technology innovations with respect to industrial XR technology and application needs and opportunities for standardisation. In the early stages of the project the research and development partners had the greatest insights, but in the latest stages the industrial Pilot partners have gained initial experience working with the new technologies and are helping to reinforce or provide further insights and recommendations.
2. For each project technology identified for standardisation, a Technology Representative is assigned from the consortium. This is typically the research and development partner that developed the technology as they were most able to express the motivations and capabilities of the technology and to carry out the initial step of preparing the specification for submission to the target standards grouping.
3. Taking due consideration of the standardisation body selection criteria (see Section 7.1), a specific standards body or community is targeted by the consortium for adopting the project technology as an eventual standard. This may be as an extension to an existing standard or as a new standard. It may be as a publication or inclusion in an industry reference open source distribution.
4. The Open Group collaborates with the Technology Representative to agree a realistic schedule for undertaking each of the common standardisation steps (see Section 7.4). The schedule is based on previous experience of consortium partners in working with the specific standards body or similar groupings, the maturity of the project technology, the experience of the Technology Representative in participating in standards groupings, and other factors.
5. The Open Group assists the Technology Representative in each of the standardisation steps to provide examples and recommendations for preparing formal submissions to standards groupings, as well as best practices for preparing the groundwork among the target standards community membership so that the submission will be favourably received.
6. The Open Group and Technology Representative collaborate with other members of the XR5.0 consortium to reinforce within the target standards community the motivation and need for standardisation of the project technology. This may be joint support actions by consortium members at standards group meetings to demonstrate critical mass of support for the project technology as a standard, or individual support actions by highly influential XR5.0 consortium members from industry (e.g. Siemens, KUKA, TAP, etc.) to help build momentum for the consensus building step. Support actions in collaboration with consortium partners may also be used to overcome potential challenges from alternative approaches less conducive to XR5.0 standardisation interests.
7. Multiple threads for standardisation of project technologies run in parallel targeting multiple standards communities each with a Technology Representative and each supported by The Open Group. The progress for each thread is tracked and resources remain available and committed after project completion to assist each Technology Representative should challenges arise or unforeseen barriers slow the action plan progress.

The strategy for standardisation coordination leverages key capabilities of the consortium partners in establishing standards, and the more than 25 years of experience of The Open Group in reaching industry consensus for IT standards, to provide an effective approach for assuring the standardisation targets for the XR5.0 project in support of European initiatives for XR platform technologies and developers are achieved.

7.5 XR5.0 technologies for standardisation and next actions

The XR5.0 project has identified three areas where technologies developed within the project are candidates for standardisation to provide improved support for adoption of XR technologies in European

industries and to extend the reach of XR5.0 tools and technologies to other application domains beyond those targeted by the Pilots in the project. These are shown, along with the targeted standards body or community and the Technology Representative partner in Table 12.

Table 12 – XR5.0 Technologies Targeted for Industry Standardisation

XR5.0 Technology	Standards Body / Community	Technology Representative / Supporting Partner
XR Reference Architecture	Architecture Forum	UBI / TOG
XR Modelling Primitives	ArchiMate Forum	UBI / TOG
IIRA extensions	Digital Twins Consortium	UBI / TOG

These project technologies that are targeted for creating new industry reference standards supporting XR-driven systems developers are described in the following sections, along with the standardisation action plans that have been established and will continue after completion of the project.

7.5.1 XR Reference Architecture

Targeted Standards Community: Architecture Forum

Description

The focus of the collaboration with the Architecture Forum is the industry consensus for an XR Reference Architecture based on the Reference Architecture developed in XR5.0 and in collaboration with the XR2Industry initiative. In addition, a specific extension that provides support for architecting XR-based systems based on the experience gained in defining the XR Reference Architecture and the XR5.0 Pilots will also be proposed. These actions would provide both formal publication of an XR Reference Architecture as an industry standard with specific methodological features included to support XR applications in the TOGAF standard, and also a community to contribute to the evolution of the XR Reference Architecture long after the XR5.0 and XR2Industry projects have completed.

Next Actions

1. Follow-up on earlier exchanges with the Architecture Forum leadership and create a XR Working Group to address extensions of TOGAF guidelines to support XR systems architecture and to publish an industry XR Reference Architecture.
2. Prepare a public specification of the XR Reference Architecture based on deliverable D2.3, and feedback and experience gained from industrial Pilot deployments and evaluations.
3. In collaboration with XR2Industry, The Open Group, and others within the consortium, launch an awareness campaign regarding the formation of the new XR Working Group.
4. Prepare a formal joint proposal from XR5.0 and XR2Industry to adopt the XR Reference Architecture specification as a first task for the new grouping on which to build consensus and support for publication of an XR focused extension to the TOGAF standard from the Architecture Forum.
5. Undertake a first set of exchanges with key actors within the new XR Working Group and others within the broader XR software development community to gain support for the formal public specification.
6. Address any issues or comments that might arise within the XR Working Group to gain acceptance and reach consensus for adoption and publication.

7.5.2 XR Modelling Primitives

Targeted Standards Community: ArchiMate Forum

Description

The focus of the collaboration with the ArchiMate Forum is to extend the ArchiMate modelling specification to include primitives that support the specification of XR-driven applications and systems. In particular, features that enable XR interactions and workflows to be more fully represented as part of ArchiMate's Visual Representation, which uses various diagrams to represent architecture clearly and concisely, making complex relationships easier to understand both by developers and end users, as well as extensions in the three core Business, Application and Technology Layers of the ArchiMate standard to include key XR related artefacts and patterns within the ArchiMate standard.

Next Actions

1. Follow-up on earlier exchanges with the ArchiMate Forum leadership concerning proposed extensions to the ArchiMate standard to address specific extensions for specifying XR-driven systems and applications.
2. Prepare a public specification of the proposed extensions based on the use of ArchiMate in XR5.0 for architecture and feedback and experience gained from industrial Pilot deployments and evaluations. The extensions are expected to be incremental revisions to be included in a future update of the ArchiMate standard publication.
3. Organise a webinar amongst the various modelling tool providers that reference ArchiMate standard compliance including the developers of the Archi open source industry reference ArchiMate tool. The webinar will introduce the proposed revisions, gather support for needed revisions and launch the consensus process.
4. Publish the propose extensions to the ArchiMate standard following the ArchiMate Forum public consultation procedures to gather comments and support for adoption of the proposed updates. Address any issues or comments to reach consensus.
5. Collaborate and provide support to the Archi tool development team to include the proposed extensions to the ArchiMate standard within the open source industry reference Archi modelling tool to encourage consistent implementations by other tool providers and accelerate time-to-market adoption of the extensions.
6. Address any issues related to tool implementation and reach consensus for adoption and publication as part of an upcoming update to the published ArchiMate standard.

7.5.3 Extensions to IIRA

Targeted Standards Community: Digital Twins Consortium (DTC)

Description

The Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) that publishes the Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA) was merged with the DTC to achieve greater collaboration and wider impact. The focus for collaboration with the DTC will be to extend the current IIRA standard with features that integrate immersive XR technologies within industrial systems architectures, and to provide reference architectural support for AI and ML components that are becoming increasingly more prevalent in industrial internet-based applications and systems. The proposed extensions would be based on the experience gained from the industrial Pilots in the XR5.0 project and would ensure alignment of the IIRA with further actions towards publication of an XR Reference Architecture standard.

Next Actions

1. Validate the use of the potential extensions to the IIRA within the XR5.0 Pilots and gain industry partner testimonials for updating the IIRA to include support for XR, AI and ML based on the XR5.0 results and X2Industry initiatives for digital transformation in industry.
2. Prepare a White Paper identifying the needed updates to the IIRA to reflect the latest technologies being used for industrial internet-based applications and identifying needed extensions to the IIRA to ensure continued use by industry.
3. Organise a webinar with the lead contributors to the latest version of the IIRA from organisations including IBM, Oracle, MITRE, SAP, Toshiba and others to present the White Paper and gain support to propose to the DTC Steering Committee continued work to update the IIRA and to call for additional participants from the DTC membership.
4. In collaboration with The Open Group and other consortium partners that are members of the DTC or its parent OMG (e.g. Siemens, KUKA,), organise an exchange with the DTC Steering Committee to request approval to launch the work and recruit members to participate in updating the IIRA specification to address XR, AI and ML technologies in industrial internet-base applications.
5. Prepare a public specification of the proposed extensions based on the XR5.0 Reference Architecture and collaboration with the XR2Industry project, along with revisions to introduce support for AI and ML components. The extensions are expected to be incremental revisions to be included in a future publication by the DTC of a next revision of the IIRA standard.
6. Address likely questions, challenges, and editing that might be proposed from within the DTC community and seek a collaborative solution to expedite the consensus process.

7.6 Collaboration and use of industry standards

To provide a broader view of the use of standards within XR5.0, Table 13 lists the current collaborations with standards organisations and communities in topics related to the project technology innovations. The table also notes the candidate targets for potential extensions to existing standards (see Section 7.5) that will be pursued as the technology development and industry validation tasks are carried out in the final months of the project.

Table 13 – Current Collaboration with SDOs

SDO/ Association Liaisons/ Working Group	Scope of Liaison / Collaboration	Technical Lead
IEEE Standards Association, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)	W3C standards have been considered in the design and development of the XR5.0 user interfaces	SPACE
Virtual Reality Industry Forum (VRIF)	XR5.0 have consulted VRIF guidelines for video interfaces	SPACE
RAMI, Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0 ⁴	RAMI4.0 was considered as a background reference model for the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
LASFA, LAsim Smart Factory ⁵	LASFA was among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI

⁴ <https://www.isa.org/intech-home/2019/march-april/features/rami-4-0-reference-architectural-model-for-industr>

⁵ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835221001455#b0355>

SDO/ Association Liaisons/ Working Group	Scope of Liaison / Collaboration	Technical Lead
SITAM, Stuttgart IT-Architecture for Manufacturing ⁶ and IVRAM, Industrial Value Chain Reference Architecture ⁷	SITAM and IVRAM were among the background reference architectures that will be used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture	UBI
Elements of EIRA for interoperability ⁸	For system engineering, we will use, adapt, and possibly extend aspects of this standard	UBI
ArchiMate for architecture design ⁹	For system engineering, the project used, adapted, and seeks to extend aspects of this standard	UBI
Elements of TOGAF for architecture design ¹⁰	For system engineering, we the project used, adapted, and seeks to extend aspects of this standard	UBI
IIRA Industrial Internet Reference Architecture ¹¹	IIRA was among the background reference architectures that was used to drive the development of the XR5.0 architecture that the project seeks to extend.	UBI

The XR5.0 standardisation lead maintains also close links and liaisons with several other XR5.0 related SDOs, including the Digital Twin Consortium (DTC), the Object Management Group (OMG), IEEE, ETSI, CEN/CENELEC, ISO/IEC 20243-2:2023: Open trusted technology provider standard; the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and the International Committee for Information Technology Standards (INCITS). As part of the implementation of the standardisation task of the project, these links may be exploited to share/contribute XR5.0 outcomes as they are made publicly available by the project.

7.7 Liaisons with and Contributions to Industrial Associations

The EU partners continue to liaise with industrial associations at the European level in order to contribute to their activities based on XR5.0 results. The scope of the contributions include participation in events and meetings organized by the associations, preparation of joint papers or contribution to whitepapers of the associations, as well as collaboration with other members around the XR5.0 technologies and use cases. Moreover, the project continues to exploit the opportunities for liaising and collaborating with associations of the Swiss Manufacturing/Industry 5.0 ecosystem, thanks to the participation of the Associated (Swiss) partners in the XR5.0 consortium. For example, SSF has promoted the project’s outcomes to its partners and members of its ecosystem in Switzerland (i.e., to approx. 3000 persons per year). Furthermore, SSF has established liaisons and exchanges with clusters and initiatives in three other sectors: the Swiss Healthtech Center, the Swiss Battery Technology Center, and the Swiss Advanced Manufacturing Center. Also, SSF has engaged with associations like the Lions Club and Industrie 2025. Moreover, LNS is part of the Swissmem association, which has more than 1250 members in the mechanical and electrical engineering industries, and has promoted XR5.0 in this community.

Table 14 provides a current list of collaborations with industrial associations by the partners. It is important to note will continue to undergo updates and improvements in the final months of the XR5.0 project as the project technologies reach higher levels of maturity.

⁶ https://www.ipvs.uni-stuttgart.de/departments/as/downloadgallery_as/groegech/Kassner_Stuttgart_IT_Architecture_for_Manufacturing.pdf

⁷ https://docs.iv-i.org/doc_161208_Industrial_Value_Chain_Reference_Architecture.pdf

⁸ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/european-interoperability-reference-architecture-eira>

⁹ <https://www.archimatetool.com>

¹⁰ <https://www.opengroup.org/togaf>

¹¹ <https://www.iiconsortium.org/iira>

Table 14 – Liaisons and Collaboration with Industrial Associations

Industrial Association / Working Group	Scope of Collaboration	Partners
Data AI and Robotics (DAIRO)	Sharing of information about the XR5.0 architectures and its alignment to DAIRO (and BDVA) reference models; Participation in DAIRO organized/supported events like the Data Week and the EBDVF	GFT, UPRC
Alliance for IoT Innovation (AIOTI)	Participation in AIOTI sponsored events (e.g., IoT Week); Contribution to the AIOTI WG11 (IoT in Manufacturing) whitepapers/documents based on the use of XR in manufacturing	UNP,
European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)	Participation in EFFRA events, project clusters and exhibitions	UNP, SUPSI, NOVA
Energistics Consortium – standards for oil/gas energy production companies	TOG hosted SDO groupings related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
Exploration, Mining, Metals & Minerals Forum	TOG hosted SDO groupings related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures as the focus of the forum is on enterprise architecture standards and reference models for the exploration, mining, metals, and minerals industries	TOG
Commercial Aviation Working Group – Commercial Aviation Reference Architecture	TOG hosted SDO groupings related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
IT4IT Forum – Reference Architecture for managing the operations of IT in enterprise and government organisations	TOG hosted SDO groupings related to XR5.0 pilots and reference architectures.	TOG
Enterprise Architecture Forum – TOGAF enterprise architecture methodology with over 100K certified IT architects around the world	TOG hosted SDO groupings addressing industry IT architecture methods and tools.	TOG
ArchiMate Forum – industry standard modelling language for enterprise architecture	TOG hosted SDO groupings addressing industry IT architecture methods and tools.	TOG
AITI Associazione Industrie Ticinesi, AGIRE, and Other EU initiatives that have AI in Industry 5.0 aspects (Circular Twain, BetterFactory, CIRCULOOS; KITT4SME, etc.)	Sharing of experience and results regarding AI and XR use cases in manufacturing; Joint meetings/workshops; Best practice sharing regarding the development of AI-based Digital Twins	SUPSI, NOVA

In line with the DoA, the project has also established liaisons with industrial associations at the National Level, such as Platform Industrie 4.0 in Germany (ATB, KUKA) and ProduTech in Portugal (UNP, IPIA). The primary goal of these collaborations have been to raise awareness about XR5.0 and engage stakeholders at the national level.

7.8 Standardization Activities within the BeyondXR cluster

XR5.0 also pursues standardization activities in the context of the BeyondXR cluster. As already outlined, the project has organized a relevant webinar (i.e., the 5th XR5.0 lead webinar of BeyondXR) with the participation of relevant projects (e.g., the OpenVerse CSA) and standards-related organizations like XR4Europe. Moreover, XR5.0 plans to participate in the BDVA’s Virtual Worlds standardization activities, which have been initiated in the context of the OpenVerse project.

8. CONCLUSION

8.1 Summary of Achievements and Concluding Remarks

This deliverable has presented the dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities undertaken during the second year (M13–M24) of the XR5.0 project. It has outlined the project’s progress in strengthening its outreach, scientific presence, and community-building efforts, including:

- The further refinement and expansion of the XR5.0 brand identity, with updated templates, visuals, and communication assets supporting consistent dissemination across all channels.
- The significant growth of the project’s digital presence, with an increase in website traffic and strengthened activity across LinkedIn, X, Facebook, and YouTube, with LinkedIn remaining the primary channel for stakeholder engagement.
- The consistent publication of high-quality and engaging content, including 25 new blog posts, regular news updates, project announcements, and four new newsletters delivered to an expanding subscriber base.
- The increase of social media outreach, with 75 original LinkedIn posts, targeted reposting activities, and cross-promotion through partner and cluster channels, resulted in improved impressions, engagement, and visibility.
- The expansion of scientific dissemination, with seven new publications in recognised international conferences and proceedings, brings the total number of scientific outputs to thirteen.
- The active participation of project partners in workshops, conferences, demonstrations, and industry events, where XR5.0 technologies, pilots, and results were presented to academic, industrial, and policymaking audiences across Europe.
- The launch of the pilot-focused dissemination series, with two out of six dedicated sessions successfully implemented (one online webinar and one on-site training), offering early insights into the project’s human-centric XR solutions.
- The consolidation and growth of the BeyondXR cluster, which expanded to thirteen projects and delivered three high-impact joint webinars during the second year, strengthened its branding, and continued monthly coordination meetings.
- The expansion and enrichment of the stakeholders’ database, which grew from 475 to 767 entries, exceeding KPI targets, and strengthened the project’s ability to engage relevant audiences in industry, research, and policy.
- The continuation of standardisation-focused activities, including ongoing liaisons with SDOs, contributions to industrial associations, and the refinement of methodological steps to prepare for future standardisation proposals. During the second year of the project’s lifetime, the project has focused its pre-standards contributions around the XR5.0 platform architecture, identified and liaised to relevant bodies, and engaged in XR standards information/experience sharing within the BeyondXR cluster.

Overall, dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities in the second year have progressed in alignment with the DoA and the project’s KPIs (see Table 15), benefiting from the maturing technical work and the increasing availability of demonstrable results. The project has succeeded in broadening its visibility, reinforcing its presence in scientific and industrial communities, and strengthening collaboration with other projects and initiatives.

Table 15-DoA KPIs VS Accomplished KPIs until M24

DoA KPIs	Accomplished KPIs until M24
Organisation/attendance to conferences/workshops (>=300 visitors, 4 speakers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE DCOSS 2005 • HOLO actively participated as an exhibitor at the XR EXPO 2025, held in Stuttgart from May 8 to May 9. During the

	<p>event, HOLO showcased its XR products and solutions – Hololight Hub, Hololight Stream and Hololight Space, drawing interest from both industry professionals and academic researchers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Humanoid Forum 2025, taking place on February 20-21 in Biel/Bienne, Switzerland. • 2025 workshop (Lucca, Italy) on June 12th, Innov-acts and Unparallel Innovation, Lda, put together a top-notch outreach effort. Innov-acts presented a paper on trusted and human-centred approaches for industrial training based on extended reality technologies leveraging an LLM server developed in the XR5.0 Project • Presentation of "UI/UX Sustainable Design: Best Practices for Applications CO2 Emissions Reduction". Presentation of the best Practices for applications CO2 emissions reduction during their design phase, with examples related to the XR5.0 project and its related applications. • The Zurich AI Conference 2025 May 13 2025 from 18:00 to 22:00 (CET) • Presentation of the XR5.0's main objectives and activities to one of ATB's interest groups; 22/11/2024; Around 11 persons attended the workshop
<p>Common activities with affiliated projects (3 common events, 4 posts in CORDIS/other EC systems)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-person meeting with XR related projects financed under H2020 and Horizon Europe. • 5 webinars with BeyondXR cluster • In progress (4 posts in CORDIS/other EC systems)
<p>Workshop/collaborative schemas with similar projects (8 project synergies, 3 common products/services)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 webinars with BeyondXR cluster • Participation in the XR2Learn Forum • In progress more common products/ services
<p>Open access exhibitions and demonstration events</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • February 20-21, 2025 International Humanoid Forum 2025, taking place on February 20-21 in Biel/Bienne, Switzerland. • Presentation of the XR5.0 Project during the International Smart Factory Summit (SSF).
<p>Onsite UC promotional demonstrations/workshops (>=1 demonstration per UC >=1 workshops per UC)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal Pilot 3 Workshop, organized by EKSO. • Pilot 4 Workshop in Lisbon 29 Oct (Physical workshop) for demo of the XR TAP training. • November 22nd, 2024 ATB had a supervisory board meeting ATB in their offices. In the end of this meeting there is always a 1 hour slot where they presented current projects of ATB. • This time, I gave an overview of XR5.0, specifically about the KUKA pilot (Pilot 1: Rapid Human Centric AI-Enabled Product Design). • Workshop - Presentation of an overview of XR5.0, specifically about the KUKA pilot (Pilot 1: Rapid Human Centric AI-Enabled Product Design). • A demo session scheduled with technicians visiting SPACE facilities for the Pilot 5 presentation (November 5th, 2025).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of the XR5.0's first results and current activities to one of ATB's interest groups 13/06/2025; Around 10 persons attended the workshop • Presentation of the XR5.0's early prototypes in Pilot 1 to one of ATB's interest groups; 12/12/2025; Around 10 persons attended the workshop.
Online and/or F2F training/webinars on Ucs (>=8 webinar/trainings >=30 attendees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 Pilot Webinars/Meetings; 2 have already been conducted, while four additional ones are planned for 2026 (i.e., the third year of the XR5.0 project lifetime).
Promotion of Results on the Future of Work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lecture in Harokopio University, Department of Informatics and Telematics covered key aspects relevant to XR5.0, specifically focusing on the architectures and implementation of Large Language Models (LLMs) for industrial training applications in Virtual Reality environments. - 40 MSc students • In person meeting with XR related projects financed under H2020 and Horizon Europe. Innov presented the XR5.0 Project at the event A2 Unit Brussels. Meeting with XR related projects financed under H2020 and Horizon Europe programmes. • Presentation of the XR5.0's early prototypes in Pilot 1 to one of ATB's interest groups; 12/12/2025; Around 10 persons attended the workshop. • UPRC is a member of the European Security and Defence College (ESDC). ESDC holds its Annual Training and Education Conference (ATEC) in Brussels in which UPRC shared some information regarding XR5.0's Training Platform and its benefits in combining Immersive environments and AI. • Presentation of XR5.0 Pilot Results and Business Models in a Workshop about "Metaverse Commercialization Opportunities" to the Doctoral Candidates of the AGORA Marie Curie Doctoral Network (December 16th, 2025)
Open access reports (>=3 journals, >=10 conference)	1 Journal Paper, 11 Conferences Paper, 1 magazine article
Non-scientific reports (>=3 industry magazines)	1 industry magazine (IPIA)
Standardisation liaisons (Standards/organisations >=3)	Standardization liaisons have been established with relevant projects (e.g., XR4ED, XR2Learn, XR2Industry, OpenVerse), industrial associations (e.g., BDVA), XR associations (e.g., XR4Europe), as well as various SDO's through TOG.
Project website with links to XR5.0 (>=1000 visits, >200 registers >=250 blog interactions)	3,000 active users on website, 7,547 impressions on blog posts, 657 sessions on blog posts.
Live audience feedback and live survey in online event (1 live audience survey in online event >= 40 responders)	Each pilot's webinar includes a live survey.

Videos, YouTube channel (1 promo/UC/tool, total >=10)	19 Videos on YouTube Channel.
Social media: ResearchGate LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, etc. (>=1500 followers, >=300 posts, >=3000 interactions)	Around 950 Followers in total, more than 400 posts, more than 2,500 interactions with more than 35,000 impressions
Marketing pack and promotional press kit (Rollup, brochure, banner, factsheet (interim and final)	Roll up banner, Brochure, Whitepaper and Press Release Templates
Project identity and branding (Logo, colour-space, artboard, graphic visuals, pitch, e-card)	Logo, Brand Identity guidelines, colour-space, visuals for each post with the specific identity.
Press releases, newsletters, and digital briefs (Y1: >=2, Y2: >=4 (1/UC) Y3: >=10 (1/UC + 1/tool))	1 Press Release, 8 Newsletters.
Stakeholders' database and engagement tracker (Y1: >=250, Y2: >=500, Y3: >=1000)	>= 760 stakeholders

8.2 Reflections and Lessons Learnt

The dissemination, communication, and standardisation activities of Year 2 proved effective in consolidating the XR5.0 brand, expanded the project's digital footprint, and helped the project to achieve and in some cases to exceed key KPIs (e.g., LinkedIn followers and engagement). The combination of diversified content (i.e., blog posts, newsletters, webinars, conference papers) and strong involvement in the BeyondXR cluster worked well in starting the build up of a vibrant ecosystem. They also helped in reinforcing XR5.0's positioning within the European XR community. Nevertheless, there are still aspects that can be improved, including:

- Finding the right balance between physical and digital events, as well as between physical and digital materials. It is envisaged that the project could benefit from face to face events much as it has leveraged digital channels and events as well.
- Leveraging the project's stakeholders' database to increase engagement in webinars, face to face events, as well as other dissemination activities that can benefit from the participation of third-party stakeholders. So far the project has not used the stakeholders' database in increasing engagement with its activities, which is probably a lost opportunity for the project.
- Engaging more actively with the Industry 5.0 Community of Practice (CoP) and the Virtual Worlds associations, as these communities can provide links to interested organizations and can strengthen the exploitation potential of the project.
- Properly communicating standardisation roadmaps and relevant content (e.g., briefs) to maximise uptake and pre-normative impact in the final project year.

Most importantly, during the final year of the project, emphasis must be also paid in planning the sustainability of the project's community. In this direction, the XR5.0 ecosystem/community could be treated as an additional exploitable asset that should be sustained and expanded beyond the end of the project.

As XR5.0 enters its final year, dissemination activities will place greater emphasis on delivering additional scientific publications, completing the pilot webinar series, advancing standardisation contributions, creating whitepapers for each pilot and maximising the project's impact through coordinated community-building efforts. Emphasis will be paid in the project's connection and collaboration with key European platforms and initiatives such as the Industry 5.0 Community of Practice and the newly established Virtual Worlds Association. The outcomes of these activities will be documented in the next WP7 deliverable (M36).

ANNEX I: XR5.0 (PUBLISHED) BLOG POSTS (M12-M24) (JAN 25 – DEC 25)

N O.	Visual	Blog Title - Linkable	LinkedIn Impressions	Publication Date	Partner
1		https://xr50.eu/blog/shaping-the-future-designing-xr5-0-architecture-for-industry-5-0-applications/	389	29/12/2024	TOG
2		https://xr50.eu/blog/xr-and-ai-in-troubleshooting-and-maintenance-an-industrial-use-case/	468	21/01/2025	LNS
3		https://xr50.eu/blog/empowering-the-future-of-industry-how-xr-ai-and-ar-are-transforming-workflows-with-realwear/	334	10/02/2025	Realwear

4	<p>Blog</p> <p>What if User Interfaces could adapt to User Characteristics and State?</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/what-if-user-interfaces-could-adapt-to-user-characteristics-and-state/</p>	246	25/02/2025	SUPSI
5	<p>Blog</p> <p>Integrating Ethics and Privacy by Design in XR5.0</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/integrating-ethics-and-privacy-by-design-in-xr5-0/</p>	163	06/03/2025	CORCOM
6	<p>Blog</p> <p>Co-Creation Workshops: A Methodology to Support Innovation in the XR5.0 Project</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/co-creation-workshops-a-methodology-to-support-innovation-in-the-xr5-0-project/</p>	216	07/03/2025	IPIA
7	<p>Blog</p> <p>Utilizing Databases for Knowledge Management in XR5.0 Remote Maintenance</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/utilizing-databases-for-knowledge-management-in-xr5-0-remote-maintenance/</p>	264	07/04/2025	OCU

8	<p>Blog</p> <p>Empowering the Future of Industry: How XR, AI, and AR Are Transforming Workflows with RealWear</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/empowering-the-future-of-industry-how-xr-ai-and-ar-are-transforming-workflows-with-realwear-2/</p>	359	29/04/2025	SSF
9	<p>Blog</p> <p>Evolving the Future: Advancing the XR5.0 Architecture for Industry 5.0 Applications</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/evolving-the-future-advancing-the-xr5-0-architecture-for-industry-5-0-applications/</p>	394	29/04/2025	TOG
10	<p>Blog</p> <p>LeanXcale is driving integration forward in XR5.0</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/leanxcale-is-driving-integration-forward-in-xr5-0/</p>	246	10/06/2025	LXS
11	<p>Blog</p> <p>Strengthening Effectiveness and Safety of Product Assembly and Repair Processes using XR Applications in the Industry 5.0 Era</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/strengthening-effectiveness-and-safety-of-product-assembly-and-repair-processes-using-xr-applications-in-the-industry-5-0-era/</p>	169	16/06/2025	SPACE
12	<p>XR5.0 Training Platform: Immersive Industrial Training for the Human-Centric Industry 5.0 Era</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/xr5-0-training-platform-immersive-industrial-training-for-the-human-centric-industry-5-0-era/</p>	565	24/06/2025	IML

13	<p>Blog</p> <p>Integrating Legacy Systems with XR5.0: Challenges and Solutions in Industrial Robotics</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/integrating-legacy-systems-with-xr5-0-challenges-and-solutions-in-industrial-robotics/</p>	234	27/06/2025	KUKA
14	<p>Blog</p> <p>Revolutionizing Industrial Knowledge Access with AI-Powered Conversational Agents</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/revolutionizing-industrial-knowledge-access-with-ai-powered-conversational-agents/</p>	79	02/07/2025	INNOV
15	<p>Blog</p> <p>Smart Pipes, Smarter Workers: How EKSO's XR5.0 Pilot is Revolutionizing Water Infrastructure (EKSO srl)</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/smart-pipes-smarter-workers-how-eksos-xr5-0-pilot-is-revolutionizing-water-infrastructure-ekso-srl/</p>	488	04/08/2025	EKSO
16	<p>Blog</p> <p>From Manuals to Mixed Reality: AI-Powered XR for Robot Assembly Line Production</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/from-manuals-to-mixed-reality-ai-powered-xr-for-robot-assembly-line-production/</p>	253	09/09/2025	HOLO

<p>17</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>On-Premises AI Utility Stack: Implementing Secure Local Language Models with Speech Processing</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/on-premises-ai-utility-stack-implementing-secure-local-language-models-with-speech-processing/</p>	<p>272</p>	<p>25/09/2025</p>	<p>SIEMENS</p>
<p>18</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>How Clawdite Human Digital Twins Empower XR5.0 Ecosystem</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/how-clawdite-human-digital-twins-empower-xr5-0-ecosystem/</p>	<p>325</p>	<p>29/09/2025</p>	<p>SUPSI</p>
<p>19</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>Mixed Reality and AI Technologies enhance SCHMIDT + HAENSCH service processes</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/mixed-reality-and-ai-technologies-enhance-schmidt-haensch-service-processes/</p>	<p>241</p>	<p>02/10/2025</p>	<p>SH</p>
<p>20</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>Building Trustworthy XR: Inside XR5.0's AI Self-Assessment</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/building-trustworthy-xr-inside-xr5-0s-ai-self-assessment/</p>	<p>268</p>	<p>09/10/2025</p>	<p>CORCOM</p>

<p>21</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>Making AI Understandable in Extended Reality: A Human-Centered Approach</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/making-ai-understandable-in-extended-reality-a-human-centered-approach/</p>	<p>368</p>	<p>14/10/2025</p>	<p>CYENS</p>
<p>22</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>LLM Agents Go to Work: How XR5.0 Is Bringing the Age of Agentic AI to Industry</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/llm-agents-go-to-work-how-xr5-0-is-bringing-the-age-of-agentic-ai-to-industry/</p>	<p>381</p>	<p>23/10/2025</p>	<p>INNOV</p>
<p>23</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>Enhancing Human-AI Collaboration in XR Environments to increase trust and human cognition.</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/enhancing-human-ai-collaboration-in-xr-environments-to-increase-trust-and-human-cognition/</p>	<p>196</p>	<p>29/10/2025</p>	<p>UPRC</p>
<p>24</p>	<p>Blog</p> <p>Human-Centered AI: The XR5.0 Project and the Future of Adaptive Systems</p>	<p>https://xr50.eu/blog/human-centered-ai-the-xr5-project-and-the-future-of-adaptive-systems/</p>	<p>402</p>	<p>31/10/2025</p>	<p>IPIA</p>

25	<p>Blog</p> <p>XR5.0 and LNS: Elevating Industrial Service Through XR and AI</p>	https://xr50.eu/blog/xr5-0-and-lns-elevating-industrial-service-through-xr-and-ai/	221	11/11/2025	LNS
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ANNEX II: XR5.0 ONLINE ANNOUNCEMENTS Y2

Placement	Quotation
<p>MASTER XR website</p>	
<p>SPIRIT website</p>	
<p>OpenVerse website</p>	
<p>SPIRIT November 2025 Newsletter</p>	<p>a new global standard for the development of Virtual Worlds and Web 4.0. OPENVERSE seeks to empower European businesses, innovators, and policymakers to shape the future of intelligent, ethical, and interoperable virtual ecosystems. Learn more</p> <p>Snapshots of the XR5.0 Pilot Demo Videos The XR5.0 project pilot videos highlight how the project is applying human-centric, AI-enabled Extended Reality (XR) to real industrial environments. Videos present practical use cases, from immersive training and process optimisation to AI-driven operator support, demonstrating how XR technologies are transforming daily workflows. Watch the series under the "Pilot Demo Videos" category Stay connected and learn more about the project</p> <p>Swarm Workshop: Programming Tools for Decentralized Intelligence and Swarms Taking place on 26-27 November 2025, Bedford Hotel, Brussels, this event will focus on the tools, technologies, solutions developed by the Horizon Europe projects on the topic of Swarm Computing. Join this 2 day event to learn about the research and innovation in the European swarm computing ecosystem. Registration is free but mandatory.</p>

Local Newspaper, Switzerland – SSF partner

ANNEX III: JOINT MEETINGS OF BEYOND XR CLUSTER

Date	Projects	Discussion Points
January 10, 2025	Master, XR2Learn, augMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Housekeeping updates, including renaming the meeting series, adding a dedicated cluster folder to the meeting notes, and granting all members organiser rights for monthly meetings. ● Development of a shared cluster identity, covering text and visual materials to strengthen the collective branding. ● Preparation of Canva templates for general use across the cluster, including templates for webinars, events, and monthly updates, aligned with existing logo colours and typography. ● Definition of a short cluster motto and verification of complete logo sets for all participating projects. ● Creation of a dedicated cluster section on project websites, featuring the cluster logo, descriptions, and all project logos. ● Planning of dissemination activities, including a joint post introducing the cluster, and coordination of promotional efforts for upcoming webinars and monthly updates.
19 February, 2025	Master, XR2Learn, augMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof, Transmixr, Sermas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Updates to the cluster’s mailing list, including addition and removal of contacts as needed; XR5.0 will distribute a follow-up email to all members. ● Discussion on moderating and potentially renaming the existing LinkedIn group: https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9300095/ ● Agreement to prepare a SharePoint document summarising the rationale for the group’s rebranding, with contributions from all projects. ● Dissemination planning, including sharing visuals for the “Women in XR” webinar and promoting it across the cluster’s channels. ● Content planning for upcoming LinkedIn posts, including the “Women in XR” webinar announcement and later the updated LinkedIn group relaunch. ● Next steps include publishing a joint news item on project websites highlighting the benefits of the cluster, and inviting additional projects to join. Pending approval, a LinkedIn “welcome” post will be prepared.
March 7, 2025	Master, XR2Learn, AugMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presentation from XR2Industry to introduce the project to the cluster. ● Information about the HECOF final event in Brussels (May 2025), including opportunities for virtual participation and presentations from cluster members. ● Review and approval of a joint webinar template to be used by all projects.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agreement among all projects to adopt the BeyondXR logo and corresponding visual identity. ● XR5.0 to re-establish the LinkedIn group, rename it to BeyondXR, and provide access to all cluster partners. ● XR2Learn proposed an extended collaborative forum and learning community, with plans to involve additional projects in the near future.
April 2, 2025	XR2Industry, XR2Learn, Master, AugMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof, Spirit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● XR5.0 reported on the success of the “Human-Centric XR” webinar, with all materials now published online following an attendance of 40 participants. ● Presentation of the “Women in XR” webinar by Vukasin, which drew 80 participants, with the recording shared afterward. ● MASTER provided updates on its second open call and requested the cluster’s support in promoting it through relevant dissemination channels. ● Discussion on community-building opportunities through the XR2Learn forum. ● augMENTOR and CORTEX2 announced a joint podcast initiative to be published on YouTube. ● Proposal by Andrea for re-establishing a rotating coordinator role and maintaining a monthly blog post to enhance cluster visibility. ● SPIRIT joined the BeyondXR LinkedIn group and committed to sharing posts among partners; a short project presentation is planned for the next meeting. ● Plans for taxonomy-style LinkedIn content categorising projects according to type and domain. ● XR5.0 to ensure that all posts related to the cluster appropriately tag participating projects.
May 7, 2025	XR2Industry, XR2Learn, Master, AugMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof, Spirit, MotivateXR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SPIRIT: presentation by Anita Gojanovic and Hermann Hellwagner. ● Dissemination: sharing guest information for the augMENTOR podcast; promotion of HECOF event (22 May, Brussels). ● XR2Learn: forum renamed to BeyondXR Forum; voting table shared; continued development of collaborative platform for XR in education. ● Cluster materials: development of a joint BeyondXR presentation; availability of updated Canva templates. ● Announcements: SPIRIT Open Call winners to be published; LinkedIn reposting encouraged; upcoming meeting presentations planned by MOTIVATE, SPIRIT, and CORTEX2.

<p>June 4, 2025</p>	<p>XR2Industry, XR2Learn, Master, AugMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof, Spirit, MotivateXR, VOXReality, OpenVerse, Sermas, Transmixr</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● XR5.0: update on the 5th webinar focusing on standardisation. ● XR2Learn: preparation for review meeting; sharing concept note and proposed agenda for the XR2Connect speed-dating event (Sept/Oct 2025). ● MASTER: second Open Call closing on 12 June. ● SPIRIT: Open Call 2 winners announced; LinkedIn promotion encouraged. ● augMENTOR: update on joint podcast episode. ● Project updates: XR4ED, MOTIVATE XR, VOXReality continue dissemination activities. ● XR2Industry: Open Call results forthcoming; Open Call 3 launching; preparation of second press release. ● OpenVerse: standardisation activities, upcoming workshops, and contributions to Virtual Worlds Observatory.
<p>July, 2, 2025</p>	<p>XR2Industry, XR2Learn, Master, AugMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof, Spirit, MotivateXR, VOXReality, OpenVerse, Sermas, Transmixr</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● XR2Learn: preparation for review meeting. ● MASTER: Open Call 2 closed with 78 applications; evaluation in progress; GA meeting held on 11 June. ● HECOF: project closure on 30 June. ● CORTEX2: preparing final event; sharing innovators' results; promoting EuroXR 2025. ● SPIRIT: amplification of EuroXR posts; assistance with under-viewed YouTube videos. ● augMENTOR, XR4ED, MOTIVATE XR, VOXReality: updates on ongoing dissemination activities. ● XR2Industry: Open Call 2 results forthcoming; Open Call 3 launched; potential participation in XR Days exhibition. ● OpenVerse: updates following review; ongoing expert recruitment for standardisation; upcoming September workshops and EuroXR engagement.
<p>October 1, 2025</p>	<p>XR2Industry, XR2Learn, Master, AugMENTOR, XR4ED, Cortex2, Hecof, Spirit, MotivateXR, VOXReality, OpenVerse, Sermas, Transmixr</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● XR5.0: discussion about how to add content to the XR2Learn forum/platform ● Plan to update and discuss the joint strategy in November ● Discussion on the structure and content of the upcoming common post ● XR2Learn, discussed of having a 30 minute session in the next meeting
<p>November 5, 2025</p>	<p>XR2Industry, XR2Learn, Master, AugMENTOR, XR4ED, Spirit, MotivateXR, OpenVerse, Sermas,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● XR5.0: Discussion about the F2F Training Session – Pilot 6 at SSF (project & pilot presentation + hands-on demo). Presentation of participation in the IEEE NFV-SDN 2025 Conference. ● OpenVerse: Organising a 90-minute workshop on XR + AI, AloT and IoT technologies on 10 December at 14:00. ● XR2Learn: Hosting a 30minute session during the BeyondXR meeting on how XR transforms industrial design, engineering, collaboration, enabling faster

		<p>prototyping, improved teamwork and immersive customer experiences.</p>
<p>December 3, 2025</p>	<p>XR2Learn, Spirit</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Share the XR2Learn webinar to increase visibility across the cluster. ● SPIRIT is reaching its end and holding its final meeting. ● Access link management: agreement on using a common email for shared access; this will be confirmed with the rest of the projects. ● Newsletter: proposal to include references to the forum and the community. ● XR4ED shared its sister-projects page for inclusion in the cluster SharePoint. ● Common post idea: year recap, key highlights, seasonal message (e.g., Merry Christmas).

ANNEX IV: AGENDAS OF BEYOND XR CLUSTER WEBINARS

3rd Webinar of XR Projects BeyondXR Cluster

“Legal Issues in Extended Reality: Balancing Innovation with Regulation”

27 January 2025, 10:00-11:00 CET

Agenda

10:00 - 10:05 (5')	<i>“Introduction to the Cluster and the Webinar”</i> John Soldatos, XR5.0 Project
10:05 - 10:25 (20')	<i>“Beyond the Dichotomy: Regulation as Catalyst of Innovation.”</i> Alessandro Paciaroni, OpenVerse Project
10:30 - 10:50 (20')	<i>“Ethical Management and AI Governance Framework in XR/AI projects”</i> Prof. Marcelo Corrales, XR5.0 Project
10:50 - 11:00 (10')	Open Discussion – Questions & Answers

4th Webinar of XR Projects BeyondXR Cluster

“Human-Centric Technologies and Applications for the Future of Extended Reality”

20 March 2025, 13:00 CET

Agenda

13:00 - 13:05	<i>“Introduction to the Webinar”</i>
13:05 - 13:20 (15’)	<i>“Adaptability of Learning process in XR Context”</i> Elena Parra Vargas, XR2Industry Project
13:20 - 13:35 (15’)	<i>“A Human-Centric Framework for XR Evaluation: Concept and Insights”</i> Konstantina Salagianni, MASTER-XR Project
13:35 - 13:50 (15’)	<i>“CORTEX2 - Augmented remote support”</i> Narek Minaskan, CORTEX2 Project
13:50 - 14:05 (15’)	<i>“The Future of Learning: How XR and AI Are Reshaping Education”</i> Epameinondas Koutavelis, HECOF and GenAI4ED projects
14:05 - 14:20 (15’)	<i>“How XR can contribute to new forms of media, art and cultural consumption”,</i> Niall Murray, TRANSMIXR Project
14:20 - 14:30	Open Discussion – Questions & Answers

5th Webinar of XR Projects BeyondXR Cluster

“Breaking Barriers: How Open XR Standards Unlock Interoperability and Compliance”

July 14th 2025, 15:00 CEST

Agenda

15:00 - 15:05	<i>“Introduction to the Webinar”</i> John Soldatos, XR5.0 Project
15:05 - 15:25 (20’)	<i>“Federated XR Content Repositories: Applying DataSpaces for XR Content Sharing”,</i> Erwin de Ley, SupportSquare – XR2Industry Project
15:25 - 15:50 (20’)	<i>“The use of standards and the challenges of standardization in the SPIRIT project”,</i> Prof. Dr. Hermann Hellwagner, University of Klagenfurt, Austria – SPIRIT project
15:50 - 16:10 (20’)	<i>“Towards a Cohesive XR Ecosystem: The Strategic Role of Standards in Europe”,</i> Michael Barngrover, XR4Europe
16:10 - 16:20	Open Discussion – Questions & Answers